

NATALIE – HORIZON-MISS-2022-CLIMA-01

„ PROVISION OF RESEARCH, ANALYSIS AND MODELING SERVICES IN THE FIELDS OF HYDROLOGY AND GEOLOGY”

WATER QUALITY ANALYSIS

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WATER QUALITY ANALYSIS

Beneficiary: VĂCĂREȘTI NATIONAL PARK ASSOCIATION
 Contract no. 4994/03.10.2024
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1. Abbreviations

NBS – Nature-Based Solutions

PNV – Văcărești Natural Park

H.G. – Government Decision

O.U.G. – Government Emergency Ordinance

Ord. – Order

CE – European Commission

UE – European Union

C & I – Research and Innovation

SEC – European Research Area

ODD – Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

RWH – Rainwater Harvesting Systems

2. General Data

This document represents the Study on Water Quality Analysis within the framework of Research, Analysis, and Modeling Services in the fields of Hydrology and Geology for the project “Natalie – Horizon – Miss – 2022 – Climate 01,” aimed at supporting the Feasibility Study for implementing nature-based green solutions (NBS) in Văcărești Natural Park.

Contract beneficiary: Văcărești Natural Park Association

3. Introduction

Văcărești Natural Park (PNV) was established by Government Decision 349/2016 and is managed by the Văcărești Natural Park Administration.

PNV was formed on the site of the former hydraulic installation "Văcărești Lake Reservoir," abandoned in 1989, and covers an area of approximately 183 hectares. After the definitive abandonment of the project, an ecosystem favorable to the development of various plant and animal species emerged, leading to the declaration of this area as a **protected natural site**, code **RONPA0954**.

3.1 Physical-geographical unit

Văcărești Natural Park is located in the Bucharest Plain, a subunit of the Vlăsia Plain, part of the Romanian Plain, in the hydrographic basin of the Argeș River, on the right terrace of its tributary, the Dâmbovița River. Biogeographically, Văcărești Natural Park is situated in the steppe region.

3.2. Location

Văcărești Natural Park is located in the southern part of Bucharest (fig. no. 1), between the neighborhoods of Timpuri Noi and Vitan to the north, and Berceni to the south, south of the Dâmbovița River, in close proximity to it, within a quadrilateral formed by four main arteries of the capital: Splaiul Unirii to the north, Șoseaua Vitan-Bârzești to the east, Șoseaua Olteniței to the south, and Calea Văcărești to the west.

3.3. Access ways

Currently, there are three access points to the park: on the embankment in front of the Asmita Gardens Complex (pedestrian access), on the embankment near the intersection of Splaiul Unirii and Șoseaua Vitan Bârzești (pedestrian access), and from Săvinești Street (pedestrian and bicycle access).

Fig. No. 1. Văcărești Natural Park

3.4. Local climate

The climate is temperate-continental, characterized by dry and hot summers and cold winters, influenced by the characteristics of the contact zone between the eastern, western, and southern continental air masses. The Crivăț, a cold and dry wind, blows from the northeast in winter.

The influence of air masses from the west and south explains the existence of long, warm autumns, mild winter days, and early springs. The air temperature regime varies between the city itself and the areas outside it.

Bucharest, with its "Bărăgan Plain" steppe-type climate, suffers from a moisture deficit compared to the optimal average value, creating a state of physical discomfort. This moisture deficit has been partially compensated by the creation of the city's lake belt, which promotes water evaporation and humidifies the air in the surrounding areas.

The urban atmosphere is subjected to a warming process through advection and radiation, due to several factors:

- Reduced terrestrial radiation in the urban area, due to warmer air near the ground, resulting from the greenhouse effect caused by air pollution with dust, gases, etc.;
- Heat loss from buildings, thermal sources, and urban heating;
- Decreased air currents due to the windbreaks created by buildings, which leads to a reduction in evapotranspiration, thus losing heat.

a) Temperature

The average annual temperature in Bucharest is around 10-11°C. The coldest month is January, with an average of -2.9°C, while the hottest month is July, with an average of 22.8°C, sometimes reaching as high as 35-40°C. In general, temperature variations between night and day are 34-35°C in winter and 20-30°C in summer.

b) Rainfall

Precipitation is low, averaging 585 mm per year, but with higher levels in summer: the largest average monthly amounts of precipitation occur in June (about 85 mm), while the lowest are in March (15 mm). On average, precipitation occurs on 117 days per year in

Bucharest. The differences in relief, nature, and the characteristics imposed by urban construction have led to the development of the following three types of microclimates:

- The microclimate of the city center, directly influenced by the density of urban buildings, where temperatures are higher, atmospheric calm and cloudiness occur more frequently.
- The microclimate of industrial areas, where fog and rain in the form of showers occur more frequently due to air impurities.
- The microclimate of peripheral residential areas, which closely resembles the natural microclimates outside the city, characterized by stronger winds and lower temperatures.

c) Winds

In general, the city territory and its surrounding areas, bordered by forests, benefit from normal air mass circulation, which is particularly favorable for maintaining a relatively stable atmosphere. The dominant winds, felt in all seasons, come from the east (21.2%), followed by those from the west (16.3%), northeast (14.2%), and southwest (11.2%). The frequency of atmospheric calm is 18.9%. Regarding wind speeds, the highest annual average values are recorded by northeast winds (2.4 m/s), followed by east and west winds (2.3 m/s). The number of days with strong winds (over 16 m/s) averages 14 days per year. As with the temperature regime, the wind analysis highlights the same distinctions between the built-up perimeter and its surrounding area. The role of the city's buildings as an obstacle causes calm conditions to occur twice as often as in the peripheral area.

3.5. Natural protected area

The main purpose of the Văcărești Natural Park is to protect and conserve the landscape ensemble, to protect biodiversity and to provide a framework for educational activities, recreation, ecotourism and scientific research.

In the Văcărești Natural Park (PNV), an aquatic ecosystem has developed over the last 22 years, consisting of wetlands, ponds, reed beds, willow groves, poplar nests, reed

and rush belts bordering the lake. These all serve as habitats, particularly for wetland birds that have started nesting and breeding here, as well as many species of reptiles, amphibians, insects, fish, and even mammals.

The vegetation in PNV is typical of wetland areas, with some notable species such as the relic of the plains *Menyanthes trifoliata*, the community interest species *Lindernia procumbens*, and *Wolffia arrhiza*, a very rare species considered nationally threatened. The park's floral inventory currently includes 102 taxa. According to the habitat descriptions in Romania, four plant communities have been identified in PNV. The dominant tree species are willow (*Salix alba* and *S. fragilis*) and poplar (*Populus alba* and *P. nigra*).

Among invertebrates, current data includes representatives from six insect orders: Odonata, Orthoptera, Mantodea, Heteroptera, Coleoptera, and Hymenoptera. Notably, a new species for Romania's fauna (*Tetramesa varia*) has been identified in Văcărești Natural Park, along with three other species first reported in the southern part of the country (*Tetramesa cereipes*, *Bruchophagus astragali*, and *Systole tuonela*).

Vertebrates include:

- Fish: crucian carp, perch, rudd, roach, bream, bleak, pike;
- Amphibians: crested newt (*Triturus cristatus*), common newt (*Triturus vulgaris*), yellow-bellied toad (*Bombina bombina*), European pond frog (*Rana ridibunda*), Eastern tree frog (*Hyla orientalis*);
- Reptiles: European pond turtle (*Emys orbicularis*), common lizard (*Lacerta viridis*), sand lizard (*Lacerta agilis*), grass snake (*Natrix natrix*), water snake (*Natrix tessellata*);
- Birds: so far, 176 species have been identified, most of which are protected nationally and internationally, including mute swan (*Cygnus olor*), white-faced tern (*Chlidonias hybridus*), titmice, ducks, herons, grebes, cormorants, egrets, ibises, seagulls, etc.;
- Mammals: field mouse (*Microtus arvalis*), pygmy shrew (*Sorex minutus*), muskrat (*Ondatra zibethica*), stoat (*Mustela nivalis*), red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*), otter (*Lutra lutra*), bats.

The Văcărești Natural Park Association, as part of the NATALIE project ("Accelerating and integrating nature-based solutions to enhance climate change resilience for various European bio-geographical regions") funded through the Horizon MISS 2022 – Climate – 01 program by the European Commission ("multi-annual investment program in research and innovation"), running from 2021 to 2027, will develop a series of research and innovation interventions needed for the ecological reconstruction of the ponds in Văcărești Natural Park (Sector 4 - Bucharest).

4. Description of the existing framework

The area targeted by the project is located in the southwest corner of the park, near the Sun Plaza shopping center, and covers an area of approximately 5 hectares.

The expected solution involves the ecological reconstruction of up to 3 ponds, each with an area of 10 m x 10 m and a variable depth of 30 cm to 50 cm.

These ponds will become habitat areas for the specific flora and fauna. The ponds will be supplied with rainwater collected from the roof of the Sun Plaza shopping center, which is currently stored in the shopping center's retention basin, along with water from the cooling system.

5. Applicable legal requirements

European legislation

Romania has been a member state of the European Union since January 1, 2007, and as such, it holds a series of rights and obligations outlined in the Accession Treaty. Romania has undertaken several firm commitments to meet European environmental standards by making investments in this field.

At the EU level, the strategic legislative acts relevant to the project's objectives are: Directive 2000/60/EC, which establishes the framework for EU water policy, amended by Directive 2008/32/EC, as well as other European environmental directives (EIA Directive – Directive 2011/92/EU revised by Directive 2014/52/EU on assessing the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment, the Habitats Directive – Directive 92/43/EEC on the conservation of habitats, the Birds Directive – Directive 2009/147/EC on the conservation of wild birds) and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2020.

Among these, the most important water directive is the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC).

The Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC - WFD) is the fundamental European directive in the water sector, promoting the concept of river basin management, establishing a framework for protecting water primarily by preventing deterioration, conserving, and improving the state of aquatic ecosystems, promoting the sustainable use of water resources in the long term, and ensuring the gradual reduction of groundwater pollution and its prevention.

The results targeted by the current project are directly related to the objectives of the Horizon MISS 2022 – Climate - 01 program.

The European Commission launched the “Mission on Adaptation” as part of the Horizon Europe 2021 – 2027 program. This represents a new approach to creating and implementing concrete solutions to the negative effects of climate change on society.

The main goal of the Mission on Climate Change Adaptation is to support at least 150 European regions and communities to increase resilience to climate change by 2030. Through the financial mechanisms of the Horizon 2021 – 2027 program, the mission stimulates the development of innovative climate adaptation solutions and encourages regions, cities, and local communities to apply for funding to develop such projects.

The Horizon Europe program MISS 2022 - Climate - 01 is part of the European initiative Horizon Europe, focusing on the mission for climate change adaptation. The objectives of this program aim to support innovation, research, and the implementation of solutions needed to address the challenges posed by climate change, improving the resilience of communities and ecosystems.

The general objectives of the program are as follows:

1. Increasing climate resilience:

- Developing solutions to help communities and regions adapt better to the impacts of climate change, such as rising temperatures, droughts, floods, and other extreme phenomena.

2. Supporting vulnerable regions and communities:

- Providing support for regions and communities most exposed to climate risks.

- Stimulating collaboration between EU member states for implementing adaptation measures.
- 3. Integrating nature-based solutions (NbS):**
 - Promoting strategies based on the use of natural resources to combat climate change and support biodiversity.
 - 4. Improving climate change adaptation governance:**
 - Supporting local and regional authorities in making decisions based on solid scientific data.
 - Developing the tools and regulatory frameworks necessary for integrating adaptation measures into national and regional plans.
 - 5. Promoting international collaboration:**
 - Stimulating the exchange of knowledge and best practices between European countries and international partners to combat the global effects of climate change.
 - 6. Driving innovation and technology:**
 - Creating advanced technological solutions for monitoring, preventing, and managing climate risks.
 - Encouraging collaboration between the public and private sectors to develop innovative solutions.

The specific objectives for MISS 2022 – Climate – 01 are outlined below:

- 1. Supporting the transformation of regions and communities into "Lighthouse Regions":**
 - Selecting model regions to implement innovative and replicable adaptation solutions.
- 2. Improving citizen participation:**
 - Creating initiatives to actively involve citizens in climate change adaptation processes.
- 3. Monitoring progress in climate change adaptation:**
 - Developing indicators and methods to evaluate the effectiveness of adaptation measures.

4. Integrating climate dimensions into other EU policies:

- o Ensuring that adaptation objectives are compatible with other Horizon Europe missions, such as biodiversity, energy, agriculture, and health.

Through these objectives, Horizon MISS 2022 – Climate - 01 contributes to building a more resilient and sustainable future in the face of climate change.

National legislation

Directive 2000/60/EC, which establishes a framework for EU water policy, has been fully transposed into Romanian legislation through **Water Law No. 107/1996**, with all amendments and supplements.

After Romania's accession to the European Union, the country included in **Government Decision No. 210/28.02.2007** provisions required by Articles 15, 16, 17, 18, and 19 related to relations with the European Commission regarding monitoring, reporting, representation in committees, and compliance verification, in order to align with the EU environmental protection acquis.

The relevant legislative framework for the project's objective is represented by **Water Law No. 107/1996**, with amendments and supplements, and **Order No. 161/2006** for the approval of the Regulations regarding **the classification of surface water quality** to establish the ecological status of water bodies. Subsequent normative acts and relevant legislative provisions are presented in the table below.

REGULATORY ACT	RELEVANT LEGISLATIVE PROVISIONS
Law 107/1996 Water Law Normative act supplemented and amended by: Law no. 310/2004 Law no. 112/2006 Decision no. 83/1997 Decision no. 948/1999 Emergency ordinance no. 107/2002 Law 404/2003 Law no. 112/2006 Emergency ordinance no. 130/2007 Emergency ordinance no. 12/2007	Establishes: ➔ a set of rules for the protection of the aquatic environment (both quantitatively and qualitatively); - the major aspects on which it intervenes; - the regime for the use of waters and riverbeds; - the servitude and expropriation regime - water management (water resources; protection of minor riverbeds, banks and management works; water management and arrangement; regime of works that are built on water or related to water; defense against floods); - flood risk management; - public participation; - control of the water management activity; - the economic mechanism in the field of water;

REGULATORY ACT	RELEVANT LEGISLATIVE PROVISIONS
<p>Emergency ordinance no. 3/2010 Law no. 146/2010 Emergency ordinance no. 64/2011 Emergency ordinance no. 71/2011 Law no. 187/2012 Emergency ordinance no. 69/2013 Law no. 153/2014 Law no. 196/2015 O.U.G. no. 94/2016 O.U.G. no. 78/2017 Law no. 243/2018 Law no. 67/2020 Law no. 122/2020 O.U.G. no. 26/2022 Law no. 90/2021 O.U.G. no. 171/2022 Law no. 61/2023 O.U.G. no. 44/2023 O.U.G. no. 52/2023 O.U.G. no. 207/2024</p> <p>Purpose: conservation, development and protection of water resources, as well as ensuring a free flow of water; protection against any form of pollution and modification of the characteristics of water resources, their banks and beds or basins, and the achievement of environmental objectives for surface and underground water bodies.</p>	<p>→ Establishes the rules for water management, covering the following areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge of water resources; - Protection of minor riverbeds, banks and water management works - Planning in the field of water management and development. - The regime of works that are performed on water or that are related to water. The placement of new economic or social objectives is prohibited, with the exception of flood defense works in the flood zone of the major riverbed or in the protection zone; - Defense against floods, dangerous meteorological phenomena and accidents at hydrotechnical constructions;
<p>Ord. no. 161/2006 for the approval of the Regulation on the classification of surface water quality in order to establish the ecological status of water bodies</p> <p>Purpose: classification of surface water quality in order to establish the ecological status of water bodies</p>	<p>Establishes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the list of biological, hydromorphological, chemical and physico-chemical quality in order to establish the ecological status of continental aquatic ecosystems - rivers and lakes, natural and artificial or irreversibly modified; - the list of microbiological, chemical and physico-chemical quality elements and quality standards in order to establish the ecological status of marine aquatic ecosystems; - the establishment of the quality status of the different water categories is done only on the basis of the quality indicators correlated with the

REGULATORY ACT	RELEVANT LEGISLATIVE PROVISIONS
	<p>different uses of the water, from the legislation in force;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - establishing the chemical status of continental aquatic ecosystems, rivers and lakes, natural and artificial or modified, is based on the quality standards for water and sediments of the quality indicators;

Harmonization of national legislation with EU legislation

The main directives and normative acts of the European Union in the field of water and environmental protection have already been transposed into the national legislation in Romania, a presentation of which is included in the table below.

COMMUNITY ACQUISITION	NATIONAL LEGISLATION
<p>Water Framework Directive no. 2000/60/EC as amended by Directives 2008/32/EC, 2008/105/EC and 2009/31/EC and Decision 2455/2001/EC</p>	<p>Water Law no. 107/1996 with all subsequent amendments and additions G.E.D. no. 12/2007 for the modification and completion of normative acts transposing the community acquis in the field of environmental protection, adopted by Law no. 161/200</p> <p>Ord. no. 161/2006 for the approval of the Regulation on the classification of surface water quality in order to establish the ecological status of water bodies</p>
<p>Directive 91/271/EEC on the treatment of urban wastewater as amended by Directive 98/15/EC and Regulation (EC) no. 1882/2003</p> <p>Amended by 398L0015</p> <p>Amended by 303R1882</p>	<p>G.D. no. 188/2002 for the approval of the rules regarding the conditions for the discharge of waste water into the aquatic environment, subsequently amended and supplemented by G.D. no. 352/2005 and G.D. no. 210/2007.</p> <p>Normative - NTPA 001/2002 "Normative regarding the establishment of pollutant loading limits of industrial and urban wastewater when discharged into natural receivers" with the amendments and additions brought by G.D. 352/2005 to G.D. 188/2002 for the approval of some rules regarding discharge conditions in the aquatic environment of wastewater.</p>
<p>Directive 2020/2184 on the quality of water intended for human consumption (reform)</p>	<p>G.D. no. 7/2023 regarding the quality of water intended for human consumption</p>
<p>Directive no. 91/676/EEC on the protection of waters against nitrate pollution from agricultural sources, amended by Regulation (EC) no. 1882/2003 – fully transposed Amended by 303R1882</p>	<p>G.D. no. 964/2000 regarding the approval of the Action Plan for the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources, amended by G.D. 1360/2005 and G.D. 210/2007.</p>
<p>Directive no. 76/464/EEC on pollution caused by certain hazardous substances discharged into the aquatic environment</p>	<p>G.D. no. 570/2016 on the approval of the Program for the gradual elimination of discharges, emissions and losses of priority hazardous substances</p>
<p>Directive no. 78/659/EEC on the quality of fresh waters that require protection or improvement in order to support fish life</p>	<p>G.D. no. 202/2002 for the approval of the Technical Norms regarding the quality of surface waters that require protection and improvement in order to support fish life, amended by GD no. 563/2006</p>

COMMUNITY ACQUISITION	NATIONAL LEGISLATION
Directive no. 2006/118/EC on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration	G.D. no. 53/2009 for the approval of the National Groundwater Protection Plan against pollution and damage, with all subsequent amendments and additions.
Directive 2006/7/EC on the management of bathing water quality and repealing Directive 76/160/EEC	G.D. no. 546/2008 regarding the management of bathing water quality, amended and supplemented by GD no. 389/2011
Directive 2008/105/EC on environmental quality standards in the field of water, amending and repealing Directives 82/176/CEE, 83/513/CEE, 84/156/CEE, 84/491/CEE, 86/280/CEE of the Council and amending Directive 2000/60/CE	G.D. no. 570/2016 on the approval of the Program for the gradual elimination of discharges, emissions and losses of priority hazardous substances
Directive 2009/90/EC establishing, pursuant to Directive 2000/60/EC, technical specifications for chemical analysis and monitoring of water status	
Directive 2013/39/EC amending Directives 2000/60/EC and 2008/105/EC with regard to priority substances in the field of water policy	
Implementing Decision (EU) 2015/495 establishing a watchlist of substances for monitoring at EU level in the field of water pursuant to Directive 2008/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council	
Directive 75/2010 on industrial emissions (prevention and integrated control of pollution)	Law no. 278/2013 on industrial emissions with subsequent amendments and additions

When developing the study, the following normative acts were also taken into account:

- The Vienna Convention on the Protection of the Ozone Layer;
- Decision 88/540/EEC on the conclusion of the Vienna Convention for the Protection of the Ozone Layer and the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer;
- The Basel Convention on the control of transboundary shipments of hazardous waste and their disposal;
- The Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants;
- Directive 2004/35/EC on environmental liability in relation to the prevention and repair of environmental damage;

6. Objectives of the water quality analysis study

Considering the main objectives of the EU and the overarching goal of the Natalie Project within the Horizon Europe MISS 2022 - Climate - 01 program, this project aims to accelerate and integrate nature-based solutions to enhance resilience to climate change.

The specific investment project objectives, focused on environmental protection and improving quality of life standards, are as follows:

- Ecological reconstruction of up to three ponds, transforming them into habitats for specific flora and fauna.
- Collection, retention, and reuse of excess rainwater that accumulates during periods of heavy rainfall.
- Resource savings by reducing expenses related to the evacuation of excess water.
- Addressing aridification issues observed in recent years in Văcărești Natural Park.
- Restoring the temporary pond networks of the park, which are vital for amphibians and the broader ecosystem that depends on them.

7. Water quality analysis

The purpose of this study is to determine the quality of rainwater and assess its potential uses for various purposes within Văcărești Natural Park.

To evaluate water quality, samples were collected on November 11, 2024, including a rainwater sample (Figure 2) from the retention reservoir located within the Sun Plaza Mall (TAP 2) commercial center, a sample from the existing pond in Văcărești Park (Figure 3). The laboratory performing the analyses is RENAR-accredited for water testing and carried out the work on behalf of the consultant.

The water samples were analyzed to determine their compliance with intended uses. Sampling locations are shown in Figure 4.

The results of the rainwater quality (rainwater and water from the cooling system) were compared with the quality parameters of surface water collected from the pond in Văcărești Park. Additionally, the quality analysis results for rainwater and surface water

were compared with the standards stipulated in Romanian legislation, which define the suitability of water in terms of surface water quality classes.

Fig. nr.2 Place of rainwater collection
(Sun Plaza Shopping Center Retention Basin)

Fig. nr.3. Surface water sampling site (Văcărești Park pond)

Fig. no. 4 Location of the Văcărești Natural Park sampling points

Rainwater originates from rainwater (collected from a section of the roof of the Sun Plaza Mall – Fig. No. 5) and from the water in the cooling system (Fig. No. 6).

Fig. No. 5. The roof of the Sun Plaza Mall shopping center

Fig. No. 6. Treatment of water from the cooling system

The roof has the following characteristics: bituminous membrane, waterproofed, slate with leaf-stopping mesh, and other physical elements. Rainwater is initially filtered through a coarse filter to remove large leaves and floating debris (regardless of the tank into which it drains).

Water, in general, is a universal natural solvent. Rainwater usually has slightly acidic properties. This property is conditioned by the dissolution of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in it. However, human activity results in the release of a large amount of harmful gases into the atmosphere, which leads to rain pollution. The content of cations and inorganic anions in rainwater depends on air pollution from transportation sources (mainly cars) and emissions from industrial enterprises.

The composition of atmospheric precipitation is conditioned by the composition of atmospheric water, the amount of dissolved dry substances in the air, the amount and nature of the precipitation. A significant role is played by the season, air temperature, weather before the rain, and wind direction. It should be noted that the rainwater collection took place in November, after a whole week of precipitation, and the cooling system at the shopping center was still functioning. It is also worth mentioning that the volume of water from the cooling system is approximately 20-30 m³ per day from April to October, while in winter the cooling system operates partially, and the water volume from it represents 10-15% of the total amount. The cooling system has the following characteristics: galvanized steel; in summer it operates 24/7 at full capacity, while in the cold season it operates at about 10-15% capacity.

The cooling water is treated and softened before being discharged into the sewer system or used for irrigation. Information about the substances used in the cooling system is provided in both the pictures below and the description. About 7-8 liters of substance are used per week.

The cooling water is treated with the following substances: HandiPak55 Cooling Inhibitor (fig. no. 7) and MB 215 - antiseptic agent (fig. no. 8).

HandiPak55 Cooling Inhibitor is a chemical additive used to protect cooling systems and equipment from corrosion and scale. In our case, this type of inhibitor is used in the cooling system.

Regarding the chemical components, HandiPak55¹ may contain the following substances:

1. Corrosion inhibitors – These chemicals are used to prevent the deterioration of metals in cooling systems.
2. Deposit inhibitors – They prevent the formation of deposits and scale in pipes and heat exchangers.
3. Material protection agents – Substances that protect equipment from the effects of high temperatures.
4. Phosphate, silicate, or amine-based additives – These substances are often used to control chemical reactions that lead to corrosion.

Fig. no. 8. HandiPak55 Cooling Inhibitor

Fig. no. 9. MB 215 - Antiseptic agent

This product is used to:

- Prevent corrosion in cooling systems;
- Reduce the formation of deposits and scale;
- Improve the thermal efficiency of equipment by preventing blockages and sediment accumulation.

¹ The specific information about MB 215 can be found in the product's technical data sheet. This sheet is not available to us at the time of the analysis.

MB 215 is an antiseptic agent used to prevent and control the development of bacteria and other microorganisms on various surfaces or in water solutions, usually in industrial or commercial environments. In our case, it is used in the cooling system as part of treatment solutions to prevent bacterial or fungal contamination, at very low concentrations.

MB 215 is a product that acts as a biocide², playing a role in combating harmful microorganisms, including bacteria, algae, or fungi. In our case, it is used for strict control of hygiene and cleanliness in the cooling system, protecting equipment from corrosion and the deposition of harmful microorganisms.

7.1. Rainwater quality analysis

The analyzes for the rainwater sample were carried out by a Renar accredited laboratory. The physico-chemical, biological and microbiological determinations are presented in the tables below, and the test reports can be found in annex 1:

² The chemical components of an antiseptic agent like MB 215 may include substances with bactericidal and fungicidal action, but for precise details about the substances contained, it is necessary to consult the product's technical data sheet. This data sheet is not available to us at the time of the analysis.

Table no. 1. Physical-chemical, chemical and microbiological determinations on rainwater samples

No. crt.	The analyzed indicator	U.M.	Rainwater values	Limit values according to Ord. 161/2006 Quality class					Values according to G.D. 100/2002 NTPA 013						G.E.D. 7/2023
				I	II	III	IV	V	A1		A2		A3		
									R	O	R	O	R	O	
I. Thermal regime and acidification															
1.	Temperature	°C	15,9	It is not normalized					22	25	22	25	22	25	-
2.	pH	pH units	7,7 20,9°C	6,5 – 8,5					6,5-8,5	-	5,5-9	-	5,5-9	-	6,5-9,5
II. Oxygen regime															
1.	Dissolved oxygen	mg/l	8,84 19,0°C	9	7	5	5	< 4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	CBO ₅	mg/l	8,4	3	5	7	20	> 20	<3	-	<5	-	<7	-	-
3.	COD-Mn	mg/l	0,43	5	10	20	50	> 50	-	-	-	-	-	-	5
4.	COD-Cr	mg/l	<30	10	25	50	125	> 125	10	-	20	-	30	-	-
III. Nutrients															
1.	Ammonium (N-NH ₄ ⁺)	mg/l	<0,02	0,4	0,8	1,2	3,2	> 3,2	0,05	-	1	1,5	2	4(C)	0,5
2.	Nitrites (N-NO ₂)	mg/l	0,01	0,01	0,03	0,06	0,3	> 0,3	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,5
3.	Nitrates (N-NO ₃)	mg/l	8,85	1	3	5,6	11,2	> 11,2	25/50	-	50	-	50	-	50
4.	Total nitrogen (N)	mg/l	<1	1,5	7	12	16	> 16	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	Soluble orthophosphates (P-PO ₄ ³⁻)	mg/l	0,42	0,1	0,2	0,4	0,9	> 0,9	0,4	-	0,7	-	0,7	-	-
6.	Total phosphorus (P)	mg/l	0,72	0,15	0,4	0,75	1,2	> 1,2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	Chlorophyll "a"***	µg/l	-	25	50	100	250	>250	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
IV. Salinity															
1.	Conductivity	µS/cm	409	It is not normal					1000	-	1000	-	1000	-	2.500
2.	Filterable residue dried at 105°C	mg/l	270	500	750	1000	1300	>1300	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	Chloride (Cl ⁻)	mg/l	20,8	25	50	250	300	>300	200	-	200	-	200	-	250
4.	Sulfate(SO ₄ ²⁺)	mg/l	36,8	60	120	250	300	>300	150	250	150	250 (C)	150	250	250
5.	Calcium (Ca ²⁺)	mg/l	31,8	50	100	200	300	>300	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	Magnesium (Mg ²⁺)	mg/l	3,84	12	50	100	200	>200	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	Sodium (Na ⁺)	mg/l	51,2	25	50	100	200	>200	-	-	-	-	-	-	200
V. Specific toxic pollutants of natural origin															

1.	Total chrome (Cr ³⁺ + Cr ⁶⁺)	µg/l	<2,0	25	50	100	250	>250	-	50	-	50	-	50	25			
2.	Copper (Cu ²⁺)	µg/l	10,5	20	30	50	100	>100	20	50 (C)	50	-	1000	-	2000			
3.	Zinc (Zn ²⁺)	µg/l	166	100	200	500	1000	>1000	500	3000	1000	5000	1000	5000	-			
4.	Arsenic (As ³⁺)	µg/l	<2,0	10	20	50	100	>100	10	50	-	50	50	100	10			
5.	Barium (Ba ²⁺)	mg/l	0,0286	0,05	0,1	0,5	1	>1	-	100	-	1000	-	1000	-			
6.	Selenium (Se ⁴⁺)	µg/l	<3,5	1	2	5	10	>10	-	10	-	10	-	10	20			
7.	Cobalt (Co ³⁺)	µg/l	1,7	10	20	50	100	>100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-			
8.	Lead (Pb)	µg/l	<2,0	5	10	25	50	>50	-	50	-	50	-	50	5			
9.	Cadmium (Cd)	µg/l	<0,4	0,5	1	2	5	>5	1	5	1	5	1	5	5			
10.	Total iron (Fe ²⁺ + Fe ³⁺)	mg/l	1,273	0,3	0,5	1,0	2	>2	0,1*	0,3*	1*	2*	1*		0,2			
11.	Mercury (Hg)	µg/l	<0,01	0,1	0,3	0,5	1	>1	0,5	1	0,5	1	0,5	1	1			
12.	Total manganese (Mn ²⁺ + Mn ⁷⁺)	mg/l	0,013	0,05	0,1	0,3	1	>1	0,05	-	0,1	-	1	-	0,05			
13.	Nickel (Ni)	µg/l	2,2	10	25	50	100	>100	-	50	-	50	-	100	20			
VI. Other relevant chemical indicators																		
1.	Total phenols (phenolic index)	µg/l	<2	1	5	20	50	>50	-	1	1	5	10	100	-			
2.	Active anionic detergents	µg/l	<100	100	200	300	500	>500	200	-	200	-	500	-	-			
3.	AOX**	µg/l	-	10	50	100	250	>250	-	-	-	-	-	-	-			
VII. Microbiological indicators																		
1.	Total coliform bacteria	no.s./100 ml	1 x 10 ²	the quality indicators will be established depending on the type of water use						50	-	5.000	-	50.000	-	0		
2.	Faecal coliform bacteria	no.s./100 ml	2							20	-	2.000	-	20.000	-	-	-	0
3.	Faecal streptococci (enterococci)	no.s./100 ml	0							20	-	1.000	-	10.000	-	-	0	

Legend:

A1 - Simple physical treatment and disinfection (for example: rapid filtration and disinfection); A2- Normal physical, chemical and disinfection treatment [for example: prechlorination, coagulation, flocculation, settling, filtration, disinfection (final chlorination)]; A3 - Physical treatment, advanced chemistry, perchlorination and disinfection [eg: intermediate chlorination, coagulation, flocculation, settling, adsorption filtration (on activated carbon), disinfection (ozonation, final chlorination)]

R- recommended values; O- mandatory values; C = exceptional climatic and geographical conditions

* dissolved form; ** - not determined; The result marked with "<" represents the value below the determination limit of the method

Table no. 2. Determinations of relevant and priority/priority hazardous substances from rainwater sample

No. crt.	The analyzed indicator	U.M.	Rainwater values	Quality standard according to Ord. 161/2006	Values according to G.D. 100/2002 NTPA 013						G.E.D. 7/2023
					A1		A2		A3		
					R	O	R	O	R	O	
A.1. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)											
1.	Anthracene	µg/l	<0,002	0,063	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	Benz-a-anthracene	µg/l	<0,002	0,01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	Benz-b-fluoranthrene	µg/l	<0,002	0,025	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	Benz-k-fluoranthene	µg/l	<0,002	0,025	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	Benz-g,h,i-perylene	µg/l	<0,002	0,025	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	Benz-a-pyrene	µg/l	<0,002	0,05	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,01
7.	Chrysene	µg/l	<0,002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8.	Fluoranthene	µg/l	<0,002	0,09	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9.	Indeno-1,2,3-cd-pyrene	µg/l	<0,002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10.	Naphthalene	µg/l	<0,002	2,4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
11.	Phenanthrene	µg/l	<0,002	0,03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12.	Pyrene	µg/l	<0,002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13.	PAHs	µg/l	<0,002	-	-	0,2	-	0,2	-	1	0,1
A2. Pesticides											
A.2.1. Organochlorine pesticides											
1.	alpha-HCH	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	beta-HCH	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	gamma-HCH (Lindan)	µg/l	<0,005	0,02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	delta-HCH	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	DDD-4,4'	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	DDT-4,4'	µg/l	<0,005	0,01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	DDE-4,4'	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8.	heptachlor	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9.	heptachlorepoide	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

10.	aldrin	µg/l	<0,005	0,01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
11.	dieldrin	µg/l	<0,005	0,01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12.	endrin	µg/l	<0,005	0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13.	alachlor	µg/l	<0,005	0,035	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14.	alfa endosulfan	µg/l	<0,005	0,00002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.2.2. Organophosphorus pesticides											
1.	malathion	µg/l	<0,003	0,0002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	parathion	µg/l	<0,003	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	dichlorvos	µg/l	<0,003	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	diazinon	µg/l	<0,003	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	chlorfenvinphos	µg/l	<0,003	0,06	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	chlorpyrifos	µg/l	<0,003	0,00046	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	methamidophos	µg/l	<0,003	0,1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8.	mevinphos	µg/l	<0,003	0,0002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.2.3. Triazine pesticides											
1.	atrazin	µg/l	<0,025	0,34	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	simazine	µg/l	<0,025	1,0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	propazine	µg/l	<0,025	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.2.4. Total pesticides											
1.	Total pesticides	µg/l	-	-	-	1	-	2,5	-	5	0,5
A.3. Solvents and chlorinated organic solvents											
A.3.1. Contains highly volatile halogenated hydrocarbons											
1.	dichloromethane	µg/l	<0,1	10/8,2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	carbon tetrachloride (tetrachloromethane)	µg/l	<0,1	7,2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	1,1-dichloroethane	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	1,2-dichloroethane	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,0
5.	1,1,1-trichloroethane	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	1,1,2-trichloroethane	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	trichloroethene	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	10
8.	tetrachloroethene	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	10

9.	1,2-dichloropropane	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10.	Highly volatile halogenated hydrocarbons	µg/l	<0,1		-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.3.2. Vinyl chloride											
1.	Vinyl chloride	µg/l	<0,1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,5
A.3.3. Benzene derivatives											
1.	chlorobenzene	µg/l	<0,1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	1,2-dichlorobenzene	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	1,3-dichlorobenzene	µg/l	<0,1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	1,4-dichlorobenzene	µg/l	<0,1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	1,2,3-trichlorobenzene	µg/l	<0,1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.3.4. Highly volatile halogenated hydrocarbons											
1.	trihalomethanes	µg/l	<0,1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	100
A.3.5. Content of benzene and some benzene derivatives (BTEX)											
1.	benzene	µg/l	<0,1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
2.	toluene (methyl-benzene)	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	ethylbenzene	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	(o,m,p)-xylene	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	BTEX	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.4. Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)											
1.	The sum of congeners 28,52,101,118,138,153,180	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.5. Other hazardous substances											
1.	total cyanides	µg/l	<30	50	-	100 50	-	1000 50	-	1000 50	50
2.	fluoride	µg/l	130	1.500	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.500
3.	petroleum hydrocarbons (content of petroleum products - global)	µg/l	<100	200	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	solvent-extractable substances	mg/l	<20	0,2	0,1	-	0,2	-	0,5	-	-

In order to analyze the quality of rainwater (rainwater and water from the cooling system, compared to the norms imposed by the legislation in force for physical-chemical, chemical and microbiological parameters, a water sample was taken for its characterization in November 2024 (sampling point retention basin Sun Plaza shopping center).

The purpose of this analysis is to establish a technical solution for the use of rainwater as surface water in order to protect and improve the environment.

In annex no. 2 shows the standards for taking water samples for physical-chemical, chemical and microbiological analyses, as well as the analytical equipment in the laboratory equipment used for specific determinations.

The analysis of the results presented in the test reports (Annex no. 1 Test reports) highlighted the following aspects:

- **from a physical-chemical parameters perspective**, rainwater corresponds to Order 161/2006 for the approval of the Normative on the classification of surface water quality in order to establish the ecological state of water bodies, for most of the analyzed indicators, with the exception of CBO₅ (8.4mg/ l) that exceeds the maximum value allowed for quality III surface water (≤ 7 mg/l), of the nitrogen ion (8.85 mg/l) which exceeds the maximum allowed value for surface water of quality III (≤ 5.6 mg/l), of orthophosphates (0.42mg/l) which exceeds the maximum value allowed for surface water of quality III (≤ 0.4 mg/l) and respectively total iron (1.273 mg/l) which is above the limit allowed for quality III of surface water (≤ 1 mg/l):
 - Slightly alkaline pH (7.7);
 - Moderate mineralization (conductivity 409 μ S/cm, dry residue at 105°C: 270 mg/l);
 - Moderate global organic load (dissolved oxygen: 8.84 mg/l; CBO₅: 8.4 mg O₂/l; COD-Cr: <30 mg O₂/l; COD-Mn: 0.43 mg O₂/l);
 - Low levels of ammonium (<0.02 mg/l) and nitrites (0.01 mg/l), with moderate levels of nitrates (8.85 mg/l);

- Moderate concentrations of phosphorus compounds (orthophosphates: 0.42 mg/l, total phosphorus: 0.72 mg/l);
 - Chlorophyll "a" was not determined by the laboratory;
 - Moderate salinity (chlorides: 20.8 mg/l; sulfates: 36.8 mg/l; calcium: 31.8 mg/l; magnesium: 3.84 mg/l; sodium: 51.2 mg/l);
 - Content of specific metals (iron, manganese) (Fe – 1,273 µg/l, Mn – 13 µg/l), the concentration of Fe is moderate and may indicate contamination from the roof (rust or other metallic materials) or from particles of atmospheric dust, instead the manganese level is low;
 - Content of toxic metals (total Cr <2.0 µg/l, Cu 10.5 µg/l, Zn 166 µg/l, As <2.0 µg/l, Ba 28.6 µg/l, Se <3 .5 µg/l, Pb <2.0 µg/l, Cd <0.4 µg/l, Hg <0.01 µg/l, Ni 2.2 µg/l, Co 1.7 µg/l) is low;
 - content of relevant chemical substances (anionic surfactants <100 µg/l, phenol index <2 µg/l, adsorbable halogenated organic compounds AOX – they were not determined by the laboratory);
 - content of relevant dangerous substances: polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) <0.002 µg/l, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB) <0.005 µg/l, organochlorine pesticides <0.005 µg/l, organophosphorus pesticides <0.003 µg/l, triazine pesticides <0.025 µg /l, volatile organic compounds (VOC <0.1 µg/l, BTEX <0.1 µg/l) petroleum products <100 µg/l, total cyanides <30 µg/l, fluorides 130 µg/l, solvent extractables <20 mg/l.
- **from a microbiological parameters perspective**, the following indicators were identified for the analyzed samples: total coliforms ($1 \cdot 10^2$ no.s./100ml), faecal coliforms (2 no.s./100ml) and faecal streptococci (0 no.s./100ml). These values are not standardized according to Order no. 161/2006 and are established according to the use of water. If we compare these indicators with the maximum permissible values according to HG 100/2002 NTPA 013 (Quality standards that surface waters used for drinking water production must meet), it is observed that the total coliform bacteria slightly exceed the permissible limit, while the other two indicators, fecal coliforms and fecal streptococci, do not exceed the limit values.

The rainwater sample, in terms of pH, falls within the recommended range of 6.5 to 8.5. This indicates a slightly alkaline water, which is normal for surface water.

The electrical conductivity is below the threshold characteristic for surface water intended for potabilization, indicating low mineralization. The dry filterable residue at 105°C complies with the admissible limit for class I surface water quality (500 mg/l).

Dissolved oxygen exceeds the minimum value for class II (>7 mg/L), indicating good oxygenation. The BOD₅ value exceeds the limits for higher classes, namely: the limit for class I is 3 mg/l, and for class II is 5 mg/l, indicating moderate organic pollution. The COD-Cr concentration exceeds the maximum allowable values for surface water (class I: ≤10 mg/l, class II: ≤25 mg/l), reflecting moderate chemical loading with hard-to-biodegrade organic substances. The COD-Mn level is well below the limit for class I (5 mg O₂/l), indicating low oxidizable loading.

Based on the analyzed data, the ammonium indicator falls within class I quality for surface water (class I: ≤0.4 mg/L). The ammonium value is excellent, indicating minimal pollution with ammoniacal nitrogen. Nitrites fall within class I quality for surface water (class I: ≤0.01 mg/L), indicating the absence of recent pollution. Nitrates fall within class IV quality for surface water (≤11.2 mg/L). This suggests the presence of pollution with nitrogen oxides, possibly from atmospheric sources or roofing material. The low total nitrogen value, below the admissible limit for class I surface water (1.5 mg/l), indicates generally low pollution with nitrogen compounds.

The values for orthophosphates and total phosphorus exceed the maximum allowable limits for class I surface water (orthophosphates ≤0.1 mg/L, total phosphorus ≤0.15 mg/L). The elevated levels may be atmospheric deposits or from additives used for the cooling system water.

The concentrations of chlorides and sulfates fall within the characteristic limits for class I surface water (250 mg/L chlorides, 200 mg/L sulfates). The calcium and magnesium content also falls within class I limits, indicating low mineralization. The sodium indicator falls within class III quality for surface water (≤100 mg/L).

The value of anionic surfactants <100 µg/l indicates a low level of these compounds, according to Order 161/2006, which does not exceed the limit allowed for water of quality I and II. The low concentration of anionic surfactants cannot affect aquatic fauna. The phenolic index value of <2 µg/l is very low and does not raise quality concerns according to the standards in Order 161/2006, which impose strict limits in class I (<1 µg/l). The presence of phenols is a major risk factor at higher concentrations, as they can have toxic effects on aquatic organisms.

Iron is a common element in the natural environment, and its concentrations in rainwater depend on atmospheric particles. A value of 1.273 mg/L is moderate (quality class IV: ≤2 mg/L) and may indicate contamination from roofing materials or atmospheric dust particles. The manganese level is low and within acceptable limits for rainwater (quality class I: ≤0.05 mg/L), without suggesting significant contamination. Chromium levels are very low and within safe limits (quality class I: 25 µg/L), indicating negligible pollution. The copper concentration is relatively low (below the permissible limit for quality class I: 20 µg/L) and may originate from water collection systems or atmospheric deposits. The moderate zinc value (166 µg/L) may come from the galvanized materials on the roof (zinc-coated steel) or from atmospheric pollution. Arsenic levels are extremely low, indicating no anthropogenic contamination. The barium concentration is low, below the limit for class I surface water: ≤0.05 µg/L. The low selenium concentration suggests negligible pollution. Lead levels are very low, indicating minimal contamination. Cadmium levels are extremely low. Mercury concentrations are insignificant, posing no pollution risks. Nickel levels are low, below the quality class I limit: 10 µg/L. The cobalt level is low and has no major impact on water quality.

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), and BTEX are present in concentrations below the maximum permissible standard limits as per Ord. 161/2006 (PAHs <0.002 µg/L, PCBs <0.005 µg/L, organochlorine pesticides <0.005 µg/L, organophosphorus pesticides <0.003 µg/L, triazine pesticides <0.025 µg/L, VOCs <0.1 µg/L, and BTEX <0.1 µg/L).

The level of petroleum products is within the permissible limit (200 µg/L) as per Ord.161/2006, suggesting minimal contamination with petroleum products. Cyanide

content is below the allowable limit ($\leq 50 \mu\text{g/L}$), indicating no toxic contamination from cyanides. The fluoride content ($130 \mu\text{g/L}$) is low, falling within class I limits ($1,500 \mu\text{g/L}$). The value of $<20 \text{ mg/L}$ for solvent-extractable substances indicates moderate surface water quality. Although lower than levels observed in cases of severe pollution, this level may signal moderate contamination with fats, hydrocarbons, or other soluble organic substances.

The total coliform bacteria value exceeds the permissible limit for surface water intended for drinking (limit: 50 no.s./100 mL). This indicates moderate contamination with bacteria from environmental or anthropogenic sources. The value for fecal coliform bacteria is within the permissible limit for surface water intended for drinking (limit: 20 no.s./100 mL), indicating very low contamination with bacteria from fecal sources. This reflects minimal anthropogenic influence. The value for fecal streptococci is excellent, below the limit (20 no.s./100 mL), confirming the absence of enterococcal fecal contamination.

Conclusion:

The analyzed rainwater indicates a moderate global organic load, as shown by the BOD_5 and COD-Cr values. This can be attributed to:

- organic matter washed off the roof (leaves, dust, bird droppings);
- contaminants from the cooling system, such as organic additives in the cooling water.

In contrast, the low COD-Mn concentration shows that easily oxidizable organic matter is low, meaning some pollutants are more stable organic compounds. The adequate level of dissolved oxygen indicates good aeration of the water.

As mentioned in the previous chapter, it appears that the water from the cooling system may introduce chemical substances, such as the biocide (to prevent the growth of microorganisms) and chemical additives (to prevent scale deposits).

The presence of nitrogen compounds in the analyzed water is low and does not indicate significant pollution. The reduced concentrations of ammonium and nitrites suggest minimal pollution, while the higher nitrate levels indicate pollution with nitrogen oxides, possibly from atmospheric sources (traffic) or roofing materials.

Moderate levels of phosphates in the rainwater suggest they may originate from atmospheric deposits or roofing materials.

The reported concentrations for anionic surfactants and the phenol index are low and do not represent a significant risk for the usual water uses.

The salinity of the rainwater is low, indicating an insignificant contribution of dissolved salts. If it were moderate, it could have been due to atmospheric pollution (industrial emissions or traffic), dust particles from human activities (e.g., construction), and roofing materials such as concrete, insulation, or contributions from cooling water.

The water in the basin contains low concentrations of specific and toxic metals, most of which fall within acceptable limits for water collected from the atmosphere and roof surfaces. Moderate concentrations of iron and zinc are likely from materials used for the roof or the water collection system. Low concentrations of copper and nickel could originate from metal components or atmospheric contaminants. The low levels of toxic metals suggest that the water is not significantly impacted by industrial or urban pollution.

The collected rainwater shows very low levels of surfactants and phenols, indicating good chemical quality regarding these parameters.

Water in the retention basin has extremely low levels of relevant hazardous substances, including priority and priority hazardous substances. Parameters indicate minimal contamination with dangerous chemicals such as PAHs, PCBs, pesticides, and volatile compounds, suggesting that the collected rainwater is not significantly affected by industrial pollution.

The microbiological quality of the water is good; however, moderate contamination with total coliform bacteria indicates slight bacteriological pollution, possibly from external sources such as runoff from roof surfaces or atmospheric deposits.

The retention basin water combined with cooling system water shows moderate quality, most likely classified as Class II. Although most parameters meet Class I standards, the organic load (BOD_5), nitrate levels, iron concentration, and presence of orthophosphates suggest moderate anthropogenic influence, requiring additional treatment before use.

7.2. Surface water quality analysis

The analyzes were carried out by a Renar accredited laboratory on surface water samples. The physico-chemical, chemical and microbiological determinations are presented in the tables below and the test reports can be found in annex 1:

Table no. 3. Physico-chemical, chemical and bacteriological determinations on surface water samples

No. crt.	The analyzed indicator	U.M.	Surface water values	Limit values according to Ord. 161/2006 Quality class					Values according to G.D. 100/2002 NTPA 013						G.E.D. 7/2023
				I	II	III	IV	V	A1		A2		A3		
									R	O	R	O	R	O	
I. Thermal regime and acidification															
1.	Temperature	°C	6,2	It is not normalized					22	25	22	25	22	25	-
2.	pH	pH units	7,4 20,8°C	6,5 – 8,5					6,5- 8,5	-	5,5-9	-	5,5-9	-	6,5-9,5
II. Oxygen regime															
1.	Dissolved oxygen	mg/l	6,83 19,3°C	9	7	5	5	< 4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	CBO ₅	mg/l	52	3	5	7	20	> 20	<3	-	<5	-	<7	-	-
3.	COD-Mn	mg/l	0,39	5	10	20	50	> 50	-	-	-	-	-	-	5
4.	COD-Cr	mg/l	1.802,4	10	25	50	125	> 125	10	-	20	-	30	-	-
III. Nutrients															
1.	Ammonium (N-NH ₄ ⁺)	mg/l	0,35	0,4	0,8	1,2	3,2	> 3,2	0,05	-	1	1,5	2	4(C)	0,5
2.	Nitrites (N-NO ₂)	mg/l	0,03	0,01	0,03	0,06	0,3	> 0,3	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,5
3.	Nitrates (N-NO ₃)	mg/l	0,96	1	3	5,6	11,2	> 11,2	25/50	-	50	-	50	-	50
4.	Total nitrogen (N)	mg/l	<1	1,5	7	12	16	> 16	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	Soluble orthophosphates (P-PO ₄ ³⁻)	mg/l	0,39	0,1	0,2	0,4	0,9	> 0,9	0,4	-	0,7	-	0,7	-	-
6.	Total phosphorus (P)	mg/l	0,52	0,15	0,4	0,75	1,2	> 1,2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	Chlorophyll "a"***	µg/l	-	25	50	100	250	>250	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
IV. Salinity															
1.	Conductivity	µS/cm	2.680	Nu este normat					1000	-	1000	-	1000	-	2.500
2.	Filterable residue dried at 105°C	mg/l	1.790	500	750	1000	1300	>1300	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	Chloride (Cl ⁻)	mg/l	379	25	50	250	300	>300	200	-	200	-	200	-	250
4.	Sulfate(SO ₄ ²⁺)	mg/l	660	60	120	250	300	>300	150	250	150	250 (C)	150	250	250
5.	Calcium (Ca ²⁺)	mg/l	262	50	100	200	300	>300	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	Magnesium (Mg ²⁺)	mg/l	142	12	50	100	200	>200	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	Sodium (Na ⁺)	mg/l	129	25	50	100	200	>200	-	-	-	-	-	-	200
V. Specific toxic pollutants of natural origin															
1.	Total chrome (Cr ³⁺ + Cr ⁶⁺)	µg/l	<2,0	25	50	100	250	>250	-	50	-	50	-	50	25
2.	Copper (Cu ²⁺)	µg/l	8,3	20	30	50	100	>100	20	50 (C)	50	-	1000	-	2000

3.	Zinc (Zn ²⁺)	µg/l	5,5	100	200	500	1000	>1000	500	3000	1000	5000	1000	5000	-	
4.	Arsenic (As ³⁺)	µg/l	<2,0	10	20	50	100	>100	10	50	-	50	50	100	10	
5.	Barium (Ba ²⁺)	mg/l	0,0514	0,05	0,1	0,5	1	>1	-	100	-	1000	-	1000	-	
6.	Selenium (Se ⁴⁺)	µg/l	<3,5	1	2	5	10	>10	-	10	-	10	-	10	20	
7.	Cobalt (Co ³⁺)	µg/l	<0,6	10	20	50	100	>100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
8.	Lead (Pb)	µg/l	<2,0	5	10	25	50	>50	-	50	-	50	-	50	5	
9.	Cadmium (Cd)	µg/l	<0,4	0,5	1	2	5	>5	1	5	1	5	1	5	5	
10.	Total iron (Fe ²⁺ + Fe ³⁺)	mg/l	0,0257	0,3	0,5	1,0	2	>2	0,1*	0,3*	1*	2*	1*	-	0,2	
11.	Mercury (Hg)	µg/l	<0,01	0,1	0,3	0,5	1	>1	0,5	1	0,5	1	0,5	1	1	
12.	Total manganese (Mn ²⁺ + Mn ⁷⁺)	mg/l	0,0372	0,05	0,1	0,3	1	>1	0,05	-	0,1	-	1	-	0,05	
13.	Nickel (Ni)	µg/l	2,7	10	25	50	100	>100	-	50	-	50	-	100	20	
VI. Other relevant chemical indicators																
1.	Total phenols (phenolic index)	µg/l	<2	1	5	20	50	>50	-	1	1	5	10	100	-	
2.	Active anionic detergents	µg/l	<100	100	200	300	500	>500	200	-	200	-	500	-	-	
3.	AOX**	µg/l	-	10	50	100	250	>250	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
VII. Microbiological indicators																
1.	Total coliform bacteria	nr.s./100m 	84 x 10 ²	the quality indicators will be established depending on the type of water use						50	-	5.000	-	50.000	-	0
2.	Faecal coliform bacteria	nr.s./100m 	3							20	-	2.000	-	20.000	-	-
3.	Faecal streptococci (enterococci)	nr.s./100m 	0							20	-	1.000	-	10.000	-	0

Legend:

A1 - Simple physical treatment and disinfection (for example: rapid filtration and disinfection); A2- Normal physical, chemical and disinfection treatment [for example: prechlorination, coagulation, flocculation, settling, filtration, disinfection (final chlorination)]; A3 - Physical treatment, advanced chemistry, perchlorination and disinfection [eg: intermediate chlorination, coagulation, flocculation, settling, adsorption filtration (on activated carbon), disinfection (ozonation, final chlorination)]

R- recommended values; O- mandatory values; C = exceptional climatic and geographical conditions;* dissolved form;** - not determined; The result marked with "<" represents the value below the determination limit of the method

Table no. 4. Determinations of relevant and priority/priority hazardous substances from surface water sample

Nr. crt.	Indicatorul analizat	U.M.	Surface water values	Quality standard according to Ord. 161/2006	Values according to G.D. 100/2002 NTPA 013						G.E.D. 7/2023
					A1		A2		A3		
					R	O	R	O	R	O	
A.1. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)											
1.	Anthracene	µg/l	<0,002	0,063	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	Benz-a-anthracene	µg/l	<0,002	0,01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	Benz-b-fluoranthrene	µg/l	<0,002	0,025	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	Benz-k-fluoranthrene	µg/l	<0,002	0,025	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	Benz-g,h,i-perylene	µg/l	<0,002	0,025	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	Benz-a-pyrene	µg/l	<0,002	0,05	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,01
7.	Chrysene	µg/l	<0,002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8.	Fluoranthene	µg/l	<0,002	0,09	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9.	Indeno-1,2,3-cd-pyrene	µg/l	<0,002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10.	Naphthalene	µg/l	<0,002	2,4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
11.	Phenanthrene	µg/l	<0,002	0,03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12.	Pyrene	µg/l	<0,002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13.	PAHs	µg/l	<0,002	-	-	0,2	-	0,2	-	1	0,1
A2. Pesticides											
A.2.1. Organochlorine pesticides											
1.	alpha-HCH	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	beta-HCH	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	gamma-HCH (Lindan)	µg/l	<0,005	0,02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	delta-HCH	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	DDD-4,4'	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	DDT-4,4'	µg/l	<0,005	0,01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	DDE-4,4'	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8.	heptachlor	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9.	heptachlorepoide	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

10.	aldrin	µg/l	<0,005	0,01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
11.	dieldrin	µg/l	<0,005	0,01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12.	endrin	µg/l	<0,005	0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13.	alachlor	µg/l	<0,005	0,035	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14.	alfa endosulfan	µg/l	<0,005	0,00002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.2.2. Organophosphorus pesticides											
1.	malathion	µg/l	<0,003	0,0002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	parathion	µg/l	<0,003	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	dichlorvos	µg/l	<0,003	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	diazinon	µg/l	<0,003	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	chlorfenvinphos	µg/l	<0,003	0,06	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	chlorpyrifos	µg/l	<0,003	0,00046	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	methamidophos	µg/l	<0,003	0,1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8.	mevinphos	µg/l	<0,003	0,0002	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.2.3. Triazine pesticides											
1.	atrazin	µg/l	<0,025	0,34	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	simazine	µg/l	<0,025	1,0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	propazine	µg/l	<0,025	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.2.4. Total pesticides											
1.	Total pesticides	µg/l	-	-	-	1	-	2,5	-	5	0,5
A.3. Solvents and chlorinated organic solvents											
A.3.1. Contains highly volatile halogenated hydrocarbons											
1.	dichloromethane	µg/l	<0,1	10/8,2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	carbon tetrachloride (tetrachloromethane)	µg/l	<0,1	7,2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	1,1-dichloroethane	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	1,2-dichloroethane	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,0
5.	1,1,1-trichloroethane	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	1,1,2-trichloroethane	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	trichloroethene	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	10
8.	tetrachloroethene	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	10

9.	1,2-dichloropropane	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10.	Highly volatile halogenated hydrocarbons	µg/l	<0,1		-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.3.2. Vinyl chloride											
1.	Vinyl chloride	µg/l	<0,1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,5
A.3.3. Benzene derivatives											
1.	chlorobenzene	µg/l	<0,1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	1,2-dichlorobenzene	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	1,3-dichlorobenzene	µg/l	<0,1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	1,4-dichlorobenzene	µg/l	<0,1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	1,2,3-trichlorobenzene	µg/l	<0,1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.3.4. Highly volatile halogenated hydrocarbons											
1.	trihalomethanes	µg/l	<0,1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	100
A.3.5. Content of benzene and some benzene derivatives (BTEX)											
1.	benzene	µg/l	<0,1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
2.	toluene (methyl-benzene)	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	ethylbenzene	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	(o,m,p)-xylene	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	BTEX	µg/l	<0,1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.4. Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)											
1.	The sum of congeners 28,52,101,118,138,153,180	µg/l	<0,005	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A.5. Other hazardous substances											
1.	total cyanides	µg/l	<30	50	-	100 50	-	1000 50	-	1000 50	50
2.	fluoride	µg/l	320	1.500	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.500
3.	petroleum hydrocarbons (content of petroleum products - global)	µg/l	<100	200	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	solvent-extractable substances	mg/l	<20	0,2	0,1	-	0,2	-	0,5	-	-

The analysis of the results presented in the test reports (Annex no. 1 Test reports) highlighted the following aspects:

- , surface water corresponds to Order 161/2006 for the approval of the Normative on the classification of surface water quality in order to establish the ecological state of water bodies, for some of the analyzed indicators, with the exception of CBO5 (52mg /l) exceeding the maximum allowed value for surface water of quality IV (≤ 20 mg/l), CCO-Cr (1,802.4 mgO₂/l), dry filterable residue at 105°C (1,790 mg/l) exceeding the maximum allowed value for surface water of quality IV (≤ 1300 mg/l), chloride concentration (379 mg/l) and sulfates (660mg/l) which exceeds the maximum value allowed for quality IV surface water (≤ 300 mg/l):
 - Slightly alkaline pH (pH 7.4);
 - High mineralization (conductivity – 2,680 μ S/cm, dry residue at 105°C – 1,790 mg/l);
 - Overall organic load ranging from moderate to severe (dissolved oxygen; biochemical oxygen demand (BOD₅); chemical oxygen demand (CODMn); chemical oxygen demand (CODCr)) present in moderate to high concentrations (dissolved O₂ – 6.83 mg/l; BOD₅ – 52 mg O₂/l; COD-Cr – 1,802.4 mg O₂/l; CODMn – 0.39 mg O₂/l);
 - Low concentrations of nitrites (0.03 mg/l) and nitrates (0.96 mg/l), but a moderate concentration of ammonium (0.35 mg/l);
 - Moderate concentrations of phosphorus compounds (orthophosphates – 0.39 mg/l; total phosphorus – 0.52 mg/l);
 - Chlorophyll “a” was not determined by the laboratory;
 - High water salinity (chlorides – 379 mg/l; sulfates – 660 mg/l; calcium – 262 mg/l; magnesium – 142 mg/l; sodium – 129 mg/l);
 - Specific metal content (iron, manganese) (Fe – 25.7 μ g/l, Mn – 37.2 μ g/l), the concentration of manganese is moderate but does not exceed the maximum concentration for surface water;

- Content of toxic metals (total Cr <2.0 µg/l, Cu 8.3 µg/l, Zn 5.5 µg/l, As <2.0 µg/l, Ba 51.4 µg/l, Se <3.5 µg/l, Pb <2.0 µg/l, Cd <0.4 µg/l, Hg <0.01 µg/l, Ni 2.7 µg/l, Co <0.6 µg/l) is low;
 - Content of relevant chemical substances (anionic surfactants <100 µg/l, phenol index <2 µg/l, adsorbable halogenated organic compounds AOX – not determined by the laboratory);
 - Content of relevant hazardous substances: polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) <0.002 µg/l, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) <0.005 µg/l, organochlorine pesticides <0.005 µg/l, organophosphorus pesticides <0.003 µg/l, triazine pesticides <0.025 µg/l, volatile organic compounds (VOCs) <0.1 µg/l, BTEX <0.1 µg/l, petroleum products <100 µg/l, total cyanides <30 µg/l, fluorides 320 µg/l, solvent-extractable substances <20 mg/l.
- **from a microbiological parameters perspective**, the following indicators were identified for the analyzed samples: total coliforms ($84 \cdot 10^2$ no.s./100 ml), fecal coliforms (3 no.s./100 ml), and fecal streptococci (0 no.s./100 ml). These values are not regulated under Order No. 161/2006 and are established depending on the water's use. If these indicators are compared to the maximum allowable values according to GD 100/2002 NTPA 013 (Quality standards for surface waters used for drinking water production), it is observed that these indicators do not exceed the limit values, except for total coliforms, which significantly exceed the limit value. This may result from discharges from anthropogenic sources.

The surface water sample, in terms of the pH indicator, falls within the recommended limits, which are generally between 6.5 and 8.5. This indicates a slightly alkaline water, which is normal for surface water.

The electrical conductivity is higher than the characteristic limits for surface water, which vary depending on the category but are generally <1,000 µS/cm. This indicates excessive mineralization, possibly caused by external sources such as industrial. The dry filterable residue at 105°C is very high compared to unpolluted surface waters (generally

<500 mg/L), suggesting a significant accumulation of mineral compounds and other dissolved substances.

The dissolved oxygen value is moderate, supporting aquatic life but may be insufficient for higher quality classes of surface water (≥ 8 mg/L for Class I). This may indicate a moderate input of organic pollutants. The BOD₅ concentration is extremely high, far exceeding the reference values for surface water (Class I: ≤ 3 mg/L, Class II: ≤ 5 mg/L). This indicates severe organic pollution, likely originating from wastewater discharges or other organic sources. The COD-Cr concentration exceeds the maximum allowable values for surface water (Class I: ≤ 10 mg/L, Class II: 25 mg/L). This reflects a very high chemical load with hard-to-biodegrade organic substances, indicating severe pollution. The COD-Mn value falls within the accepted limits for surface water (Class I: ≤ 5 mg O₂/L), indicating low contamination with easily degradable organic substances.

Based on the analyzed data, the ammonium indicator falls within Class I quality for surface water (Class I: ≤ 0.4 mg/L). The level suggests low contamination with ammoniacal nitrogen. The nitrite indicator falls within Class II quality for surface water (Class I: ≤ 0.01 mg/L; Class II: ≤ 0.03 mg/L), indicating moderate contamination. The nitrate indicator falls within Class I quality for surface water (≤ 1 mg/L), suggesting low contamination with oxidized nitrogen, typical of clean waters.

The values for orthophosphates and total phosphorus exceed the maximum allowable values for Class I surface water (orthophosphates ≤ 0.1 mg/L, total phosphorus ≤ 0.15 mg/L). The elevated levels can be attributed to nutrient inputs from anthropogenic sources...

The high chloride concentration compared to the characteristic limits for Class I and II surface water (≤ 25 mg/L and ≤ 50 mg/L, respectively) indicates saline pollution. The sulfate level, which is far above the characteristic limits for surface water (< 300 mg/L), suggests significant contamination from industrial or natural sources. The high calcium and magnesium content indicates very hard water, which is unusual for surface water. This could result from mineral inputs from local rocks or pollution. The sodium indicator falls within Class IV quality for surface water (≤ 200 mg/L).

The reported value of <100 µg/l for anionic surfactants is in compliance with the acceptable limits for water quality classes I and II according to Order 161/2006. This value suggests a low level of contamination and a minimal impact on aquatic ecosystems. At higher concentrations, anionic surfactants can affect the surface tension of water, negatively influencing aquatic organisms. The reported value of <2 µg/l for the phenol index is in line with the standards for class I surface water quality according to Order 161/2006, which sets the maximum limit for phenols at 1 µg/l in class I and 5 µg/l in class II. At this low concentration, phenols do not present a significant ecological risk. If the value exceeds the limits, toxic impacts on aquatic flora and fauna may occur.

Iron is below the allowable limit for Class I surface water (≤ 300 µg/L). Iron at this concentration does not indicate a significant problem and complies with quality standards. Manganese does not exceed the characteristic levels for Class I surface water (≤ 50 µg/L). The low levels of chromium (<2.0 µg/L) suggest an absence of chromium contamination. Copper is well below the allowable limit for Class I (≤ 20 µg/L). The zinc content is very low compared to the Class I limit (≤ 200 µg/L) and is characteristic of unpolluted waters. There are no signs of arsenic contamination, as its concentration is below the allowable limit for Class I (≤ 10 µg/L). The level of barium suggests a natural presence without significant polluting impact. There is no significant selenium contamination. The concentration of lead (<2.0 µg/L) and cadmium (<0.4 µg/L) is very low, characteristic of unpolluted waters. The mercury content is below the allowable limit for Class I (≤ 0.05 µg/L), and the nickel level is low (≤ 20 µg/L), indicating good water quality. The low cobalt concentration (<0.6 µg/L) does not indicate pollution.

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are found in concentrations of <0.002 µg/L. This value indicates the absence of PAH contamination, which are carcinogenic pollutants. The value for polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) (<0.005 µg/L) suggests no significant PCB contamination, which are persistent and toxic substances. The levels of pesticides (organochlorine pesticides <0.005 µg/L, organophosphorus pesticides <0.003 µg/L, and triazine pesticides <0.025 µg/L) indicate negligible contamination. The value for volatile organic compounds (VOCs) (<0.1 µg/L) suggests an absence of significant VOC contamination. The BTEX concentration (<0.1 µg/L) is low, indicating no pollution with

benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene, toxic hydrocarbons associated with the petrochemical industry.

The value for petroleum products falls within the allowable limit (200 µg/L) according to Order 161/2006, suggesting low contamination with petroleum products. The cyanide content is below the allowable limit (≤ 50 µg/L) and indicates the absence of toxic cyanide contamination. The fluoride content is low (320 µg/L), indicating minimal natural or anthropogenic contamination. The value of < 20 mg/L for solvent-extractable substances indicates moderate quality of surface water. Although lower than levels observed in cases of severe pollution, this level may signal moderate contamination with fats, hydrocarbons, or other soluble organic substances.

The value of total coliforms exceeds the allowable limit both for surface water intended for potabilization and for water intended for human consumption, serving as an indicator of general contamination. The level of fecal coliforms is low compared to the allowable limit for surface water intended for potabilization, suggesting the absence of significant recent fecal contamination. The absence of fecal streptococci confirms the lack of a direct or recent fecal source.

Concluzie

The surface water sample shows severe organic pollution. The very high concentrations of BOD5 and COD-Cr indicate an **excessive organic and chemical load**, incompatible with higher quality standards for surface water.

The **conductivity** and levels of **chlorides, sulfates, calcium, and magnesium** suggest excessively mineralized water, with potential sources of pollution from **salts** or anthropogenic activities.

The concentrations of ammonium, nitrites, and nitrates are within the limits for Class I and II water quality, indicating low nitrogen contamination.

The concentrations of orthophosphates and total phosphorus exceed the allowable limits for Class I and II, which may lead to water eutrophication.

The analyzed indicators (anionic surfactants and phenolic index) suggest good surface water quality, in accordance with class I standards of Order 161/2006.

The concentrations of specific metals and toxic metals do not exceed the maximum allowable limits for Class I surface water quality. This indicates an absence of significant metal contamination, and the analyzed values are characteristic of surface water with very low anthropogenic influence.

The low values of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), pesticides, BTEX, volatile organic compounds (VOCs), and other toxic substances indicate unpolluted water regarding hazardous and priority hazardous substances. The value for extractable substances suggests moderate pollution, with anthropogenic influences that may result from occasional discharges or runoff from human activities.

The quality of surface water from the perspective of microbiological indicators is unsatisfactory due to the high level of total coliforms, which indicates general contamination. However, the low concentrations of fecal coliforms and fecal streptococci suggest that there is no severe recent fecal contamination, and the source of pollution is likely mixed.

7.3. Analysis of Rainwater Quality Compared to Surface Water Quality

7.3.1. Analysis of Microbiological Indicators

The results in Table 1 and Table 3 for the microbiological indicators, total coliforms, show significant differences. The surface water collected at point P1 contains a significantly higher number of total coliforms than the rainwater (P2). Total coliforms in rainwater (P2) showed a slight exceedance over the limit value set for surface water for potable water (Table 1). This contamination of the rainwater may have been influenced by external sources, such as runoff from the roof surfaces or atmospheric deposits.

The surface water collected at point P1 showed a slightly higher number of fecal coliform bacteria compared to the rainwater collected at point P2. Both samples did not exceed the limit value set for surface water for potable water (Table 1 and Table 3).

No differences were observed for fecal streptococci (enterococci) in either the rainwater or the surface water. These indicators did not exceed the permissible limit.

7.3.2. Analysis of physicochemical indicators

There were no significant differences in pH between the rainwater collected at point P2 and the surface water (P1). The values fell within the permissible limit for surface water.

The rainwater collected at point P2 showed much better electrical conductivity (5 times lower) compared to the surface water collected at point P1. For this reason, the surface water is extremely mineralized and indicates pollution caused by external sources. The permissible limit for surface water was exceeded in the sample collected at point P2, which showed a value 2.5 times higher than the standard.

The analyses showed significant differences in the dried filterable residue at 105°C between the different water types. The lowest residue value was obtained for the rainwater collected at P2, with a value of 270 mg/l. The value for surface water was approximately 6.6 times higher than the value for rainwater. Surface water with a residue of 1,790 mg/L far exceeds the permissible limits even for Class II, indicating significant contamination. Rainwater has a low residue, making it much closer to quality standards. Surface water is much more polluted than rainwater, and the residue value indicates significant loading with dissolved compounds.

Rainwater showed a higher concentration of dissolved oxygen (8.84 mg/l) compared to surface water (6.83 mg/l), suggesting that the rainwater is less polluted organically. A higher concentration of dissolved oxygen is favorable for aquatic life, and rainwater appears to support aquatic ecosystems better. Both water types meet quality standards, but rainwater contains more dissolved oxygen.

Significant differences were recorded for BOD₅ and COD-Cr for the two types of water analyzed. The BOD₅ value is 6 times higher in the surface water collected at point P1 than in rainwater (P2), indicating greater organic pollution, as BOD₅ measures the amount of oxygen consumed by microorganisms breaking down organic matter. Rainwater has an extremely low COD-Cr level compared to surface water, suggesting

that it is much less chemically polluted. No significant differences were recorded between the COD-Mn concentrations in rainwater and surface water, indicating a similar level of lightly degradable organic pollution in both water types. This represents a low level of pollution, and the differences are not significant. Compliance with the surface water standard for rainwater was 100% for P2 for this indicator. Rainwater has a lower organic load than surface water and largely meets the quality limits set by Order 161/2006, showing light organic and chemical pollution.

The increased ammonium ion content (0.35 mg/l) in the surface water sample collected at point P1 indicates significant contamination, possibly from anthropogenic sources or natural biological processes. Surface water has a higher ammonium pollution level (approximately 18 times higher) than rainwater, signifying a greater impact on water quality. Rainwater complies 100% with the accepted ammonium limit compared to surface water. No significant differences were recorded for nitrites in both water samples. The nitrite level in surface water is slightly higher than in rainwater. Rainwater is 100% compliant with the surface water quality standard. The nitrate level in rainwater is 9 times higher than in surface water, possibly originating from atmospheric sources or roofing material. The orthophosphate values for both water types are quite similar and do not exceed the general limit of 0.4 mg/L for surface water of quality III. The total phosphorus content in rainwater collected at point P2 is 1.4 times higher than in surface water.

From a nutrient perspective, rainwater better complies with the quality standards of Order 161/2006, having values below the accepted limits for all indicators, except for the slightly higher nitrite level and the orthophosphate and total phosphorus levels, which comply with the limit for quality III water.

The analyses showed significant differences in salinity between the two water samples. The concentration of chlorides and sulfates in surface water is significantly higher (18 times higher) than in rainwater. Rainwater fully complied with the limit for quality I water according to Order 161/2006. A lower calcium level was recorded in rainwater, being 8 times lower than in the surface water sample collected at point P2. This suggests that surface water is harder. Similarly to calcium, surface water contains much more

magnesium, which contributes to water hardness. Regarding the sodium ion concentration, it was much lower in rainwater.

Rainwater has much lower levels of these substances (chlorides, sulfates, calcium, magnesium, and sodium), making it less polluted compared to surface water.

There were significant differences in the iron content in the analyzed waters, mainly due to the increased content in rainwater. The value was four times higher than the accepted limit for class I, indicating significant iron contamination, possibly due to contamination from the roof (rust or other metal materials), the cooling system, or atmospheric dust particles. The iron content in the surface water sample collected at point P1 is 25.7 µg/L, well below the accepted limit for class I, suggesting very good quality from this perspective. The manganese level in surface water was below the accepted limit for class I but nearly three times higher than in rainwater. Rainwater shows high iron contamination, exceeding the accepted limits for class I, which places it in a lower quality class.

No significant differences were recorded for the following toxic metals: chromium, arsenic, selenium, lead, cadmium, and mercury. The values were identical and comply with the accepted limits for class I according to Order 161/2006. The zinc concentration is significantly higher in rainwater (166 µg/L) compared to surface water (5.5 µg/L). The increased levels in rainwater may be caused by the corrosion of roofing materials or cooling systems. Its value in surface water is below the accepted limit for class I (100 µg/L). Copper is higher in rainwater (10.5 µg/L) compared to surface water (8.3 µg/L), but remains below the accepted limit for class I water quality (20 µg/L), according to Order 161/2006. The cause might be attributed to metal water collection systems. The barium level is 1.8 times higher in surface water compared to rainwater. Possible sources for surface water could be due to natural geological influences. Rainwater shows a cobalt level 2.8 times higher than surface water. The difference in cobalt content between the two water samples may stem from industrial influences or metal materials in the collection systems.

Rainwater has higher levels of zinc, copper, and cobalt, possibly from anthropogenic sources, while surface water has higher levels of barium and nickel, likely from natural sources. The values of these indicators in rainwater fall within the limits for class I water quality according to Order 161/2006, except for zinc, which falls within the limit for class II water quality.

No differences were recorded between the anionic surfactants and phenol index in the two water samples. Both indicators (anionic surfactants and phenol index) fall within the quality standards for class I surface water according to Order 161/2006. The similar values indicate that rainwater does not show additional contamination compared to surface water from the perspective of these parameters.

7.3.3. Analysis of relevant chemical indicators

The values for PAHs, PCBs, pesticides (organochlorines, organophosphates, triazines), VOCs, BTEX, petroleum products, total cyanides, and extractable substances are the same in both samples. This indicates the lack of significant differences between rainwater and surface water for these parameters. All these values are within the acceptable limits according to Ord. 161/2006, Class I.

The fluoride concentration in surface water is 2.46 times higher than that in rainwater. Both values are well below the permissible limit of 1.5 mg/L according to Class I standards.

Rainwater and surface water show similar indicators for most chemical and pollution parameters, with no exceedances of the acceptable limits for Class I according to Ord. 161/2006. The only difference is in the case of fluorides, which are higher in surface water, but still within the quality limits.

Conclusion:

The collected rainwater has significantly better chemical and physical quality than surface water, with lower values for mineralization, organic load, salinity, and toxic metals. However, the presence of relatively higher concentrations of nitrites, phosphates, and iron may suggest local influences from the collection sources (e.g., covered surfaces, atmospheric deposits).

Thus, rainwater can be considered a valuable resource for non-potable uses. However, an appropriate treatment and management process is recommended based on the intended purpose (e.g., irrigation, cleaning, industrial cooling, or other non-potable uses), as well as periodic monitoring of its quality, particularly for water from the cooling system.

8. Recommendations for Rainwater Reuse

Recently, there has been an increasing global discussion about the possibility of using rainwater for various purposes. This discussion has gained momentum due to climate change and the growing water deficit in many countries. Rainwater harvesting and its use can improve water security and access to water. Numerous studies have shown that rainwater harvesting systems (RWH) can supply up to 100% of the water needed for a household.³

The quality of rainwater depends on the geographic area and anthropogenic factors. Additionally, the quality of rainwater collected from rooftops depends on⁴:

(1) the roofing material (chemical properties, roughness, coverage area, age, etc.) – in our project, this includes bituminous membrane, waterproofing, slate with leaf traps, and other physical elements,

(2) limiting physical conditions (size, slope, direction, and exposure),

(3) roof location (distance from potential pollution sources) – the distance between the South Thermal Power Plant and the Sun Plaza shopping center is approximately 2.7 km, the distance between the shopping center and major streets: Calea Văcărești – 0.3 km; Splaiul Unirii – 1.5 km; Șoseaua Vitan Bârzești – 1.6 km; Șoseaua Olteniței – 0.17 km,

(4) concentrations of chemical contaminants (vapor pressure, pollutant solubility in water, etc.) – these data are found in Chapter 7.1 and in Annex 1,

³ "Assessment of Rainwater Quality Regarding Its Use in the Roztocze National Park (Poland)—Case Study", *Water and Wastewater Management in Agriculture*, Appl. Sci.2023, 13(10),6110

⁴ "Forster, J. The influence of location and season on the concentrations of macroions and organic trace pollutants in roof runoff", *Water Sci. Technol.* 1998, 38, 83–90

(5) precipitation event characteristics (intensity and volume of atmospheric precipitation, wind characteristics, pollutant concentrations in precipitation waters) – these data are presented in Chapters 3.4, 7.1, and

(6) local meteorological factors (season of the year, weather characteristics, duration of the previous dry period).

Rainwater collected typically has good physicochemical parameters but often contains high levels of microbial contaminants. In our study, the microbiological quality of the rainwater sample collected at point P2 is good, but it shows moderate contamination with total coliform bacteria, indicating slight bacterial pollution.

The pollution of collected rainwater can be attributed to vehicle and building fuel combustion, industrial emissions, agricultural activities in rural areas, and fecal deposits from animals, mainly birds. In our study, the analysis of the rainwater sample revealed that, although most parameters comply with Class I standards, the organic load (BOD_5), nitrate levels, iron concentration, and the presence of orthophosphates suggest moderate anthropogenic influence.

The quality of rainwater also depends on storage conditions. Quality evaluation data for rainwater stored in different types of cisterns have been reported by Wu et al. These authors showed that concrete reservoirs are the best solution for storing rainwater. In this study, rainwater is collected in a retention basin made of concrete, waterproofed with a rubber membrane.

From the previous studies presented, it is evident that rainwater can act as:

- a free and inexhaustible water source;
- a source for addressing water shortages;
- a source for reducing flood damage;
- protection for the durability of water reserves;
- conservation of natural resources;
- a source of drought resistance (agriculture, public sector, or industry).

Rainwater is a mixed electrolyte that contains varying amounts of major and minor ions. Sodium, potassium, magnesium, calcium, chloride, bicarbonate, and sulfate ions are the major constituents, along with ammonia, nitrates, nitrites, nitrogen, and other nitrogen compounds.

a) A free and inexhaustible source of water

Rainwater is a natural, free, and inexhaustible source of water. This water is collected during the rainy seasons and stored for use during dry periods. It is a safe and efficient way to obtain drinking water.

Fig. no. 10. Rainwater, an inexhaustible source of water

b) Source for solving water deficiency

Due to the growing population, water deficiency is another issue faced by many people worldwide. Collecting and storing rainwater provides a simple and effective solution to this problem.

Fig. no. 11. Rainwater as a source for saving drinking water

This method can be used in areas where there is a sufficient amount of precipitation and adequate infrastructure for collecting, storing, and distributing this water.

c) Source of reducing flood damage

Rainwater collection helps reduce flood damage. In the case of heavy rainfall, water floods roads, parking lots, building rooftops, so it is not collected or absorbed by the ground. This surplus of water washes heavily polluted areas and flows into underground waters, rivers, lakes, etc.

Collecting water before it reaches polluted surfaces prevents the infiltration of sediments and chemicals into the watercourse.

Fig. no. 12. Rainwater as a source of collection

Collecting rainwater reduces these water quantities and, as a result, reduces the likelihood of flooding.

d) Protection of water reserve sustainability

Collecting rainwater helps maintain the sustainability of water reserves. Extracting water from rivers, lakes, or wells can disrupt the ecosystem, harming these places and reducing the available water quantities. Collecting rainwater helps prevent this issue because this method does not affect the water level in an ecosystem. Therefore, collecting rainwater contributes to preserving the sustainability of water reserves.

e) Saving natural resources

Collecting rainwater helps save natural resources. Extracting water from these sources involves electricity consumption, in the form of electric pumps, to power the extraction process. Collecting rainwater is a process that does not require electricity or other resources to be carried out. This means that collecting rainwater contributes to saving energy consumption and, therefore, reducing the amounts of fossil fuels needed to produce it.

f) Source of drought resistance

During periods of drought, authorities could use rainwater for agricultural, urban, and industrial purposes. Using rainwater in agriculture can provide a reliable source of water for irrigation for farmers.

There are cases where rainwater is often used to irrigate non-agricultural lands, such as parks, golf courses, green spaces, gardens, highways, or

Fig. no. 14. Rainwater as a source of drought resilience

to replace drinking water used for toilet flushing.

According to the data provided by the Laboratory on December 12, 2024, regarding the quality indicators of the rainwater sample, it is observed that the rainwater sample has a quality that could make it suitable to be used as a water source for other uses (public domain), protecting and improving the environment, as it does not contain specific toxic substances above the maximum admissible value, but it does require initial treatment.

Conclusion

Rainwater harvesting is a practical and efficient solution to address the issue of water scarcity. This method offers numerous benefits, including the conservation of natural resources, ecosystem protection, and a free source of water for agriculture.

The rainwater collected in the retention basin at Sun Plaza Mall, after treatment, could be used for:

- park irrigation

- industrial uses: in the cooling system
- washing: cleaning the streets adjacent to Sun Plaza Mall
- toilet water supply: for Sun Plaza Mall and nearby buildings
- restoration of amphibian habitats in Văcărești Natural Park.

9. Conclusion

Rainwater from the retention basin combined with water from the cooling system presents a moderate quality, most likely classified as Class II. Although most parameters comply with Class I standards, the organic load (BOD₅), nitrate levels, iron concentration, and the presence of orthophosphates suggest moderate anthropogenic influence, requiring additional treatment before use.

The collected rainwater has significantly better chemical and physical quality than surface water, with lower values for mineralization, organic load, salinity, and toxic metals. However, the presence of relatively higher concentrations of nitrites, phosphates, and iron may suggest local influences from the collection sources (e.g., covered surfaces, atmospheric deposits).

Thus, rainwater can be considered a valuable resource for non-potable uses, but proper treatment and management processes are recommended depending on the intended purpose (e.g., irrigation, washing, industrial cooling, or other non-potable uses), as well as periodic quality monitoring, especially for water from the cooling system.

Therefore, the collection of rainwater from Sun Plaza Mall represents a sustainable solution to meet household needs (toilet water for Sun Plaza Mall and nearby buildings), as well as to protect and improve the surrounding environment (restoration of amphibian habitats in Văcărești Natural Park, park irrigation, and cleaning the streets adjacent to Sun Plaza Mall).

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RAPORT DE ÎNCERCARE Nr. 3465/1-AINS din 11.12.2024

Denumire și adresă client: AQUAPROIECT S.A. BUCUREȘTI,

Splaiul Independentei nr. 294, Sector 6, Bucuresti

Comanda nr.: 17607/11.11.2024

Data primirii probelor: 18.11.2024

Perioada executării încercărilor: 18.11.-05.12.2024

Date de identificare a probelor: apa suprafața

8056-AINS - apa suprafața – apa din iazurile din Parcul Natural Vacaresti

Încercări executate: Temperatura, pH, Oxigen dizolvat, CBO₅, CCOCr, Indice de permanganat, Amoniu, Nitriti, Azotați, Azot total, Fosfați, Fosfor total, Conductivitate electrica la 25°C, Reziduu filtrabil uscat la 105°C (TDS), Cloruri, Sulfati, Calciu, Magneziu, Sodiu, Fluoruri, Crom total, Cupru, Zinc, Arsen, Bariu, Cobalt, Plumb, Cadmiu, Fier total, Seleniu, Mercur, Mangan, Nichel, Indice de fenol, Continut de produse petroliere, Substante extractibile cu solvenți, Hidrocarburi aromatice policiclice (HAP):[Antracen, Benz(a)antracen, Benz(b)fluoranten, Benz(k)fluoranten, Benz(ghi)perilen, Benz(a)piren, Crisen, Fluoranten, Indeno(1,2,3-cd)piren, Naftalina, Fenantren, Piren], Pesticide organoclorurate: [alfa-HCH, beta-HCH, gama-HCH, delta-HCH, 4,4'-DDD, 4,4'-DDT, 4,4'-DDE, Heptaclor, Heptacloropoxid, Aldrin, Dieldrin, Endrin, Alaclor, alfa-endosulfan], Pesticide triazinice: [Simazin, Atrazin, Propazin], Pesticide fosforice:[Malation, Paration, Diclervos, Diazinon, Clorfenvinfos, Clorpirifos, Metamidofos, Mevinfos], Hidrocarburi halogenate foarte volatile:[Diclrometan, Tetraclorura de carbon, 1,1-dicloroetan, 1,2-dicloroetan, 1,1,1-tricloroetan, 1,1,2-tricloroetan, Tricloroetena, Tetracloroetena, 1,2-dicloropropan, Clorura de vinil], Clorobenzen, 1,2-diclorobenzen, 1,3-diclorobenzen, 1,4-diclorobenzen, 1,2,3-triclorobenzen, 1,2,4-triclorobenzen, Trihalometani (Cloroform), BTEX: [Benzen, Toluen, Etilbenzen, (o,m,p-Xileni)], Policlorbifenili (PCB) suma congenerilor 28,52,101,118,138,153,180 , Cianuri totale, Agenti de suprafața anionici - MBAS masurarea indicelui de albastru de metilen.

Modul de prelevare și conservare a probei: Proba a fost prelevata de INCD-ECOIND conform Raportului de prelevare-conservare nr. Rpc. 388-BIOL/18.11.2024, respectandu-se indicatiile normativelor privind prelevarea, conservarea si transportul probelor de apa.

Rezultatele prezentate in Raportul de Incercare se refera numai la proba supusa incercarii.

Se interzice reproducerea Raportului de Incercare in alte scopuri decat cel pentru care a fost eliberat sau reproducerea partiala a Raportului de Incercare fara acordul scris al INCD-ECOIND.

Executant: Departament Control Poluare, Laborator Control Poluare Ape, Sol, Deseuri (AINS), Laborator Bioteste - Analize Biologice (BIOL)

DIRECTOR GENERAL,

Dr. Chim. Luana Florentina PASCU

Sef Laborator,

Dr. Chim. Florentina Laura CHIRIAC

Raport de Incercare întocmit în 2 exemplare din care exemplarul 1 la client.

Acest raport va fi însoțit de Raportul de Incercare nr. 1035/1-BIOL/2024, emis de Laboratorul Bioteste-Analize biologice din Drumul Podu Dambovitei nr. 57-73, sector 6, Bucuresti avand Certificatul de acreditare LI941 - actualizat in data de 21.12.2023

Nr. Crt	Incercare executată	UM	Simbol probă/ valori determinate	Metoda de încercare
			8056-AINS	
1	Temperatura ^{2),*}	°C	6.2	Procedura operationala de lucru POL-46N
2	pH ^{1), 2)}	unitati de pH	7.4 20.8°C	SR EN ISO 10523:2012
3	Oxigen dizolvat ^{1),2),*}	mgO ₂ /L	6.83 19.3°C	SR EN ISO 5814:2013
4	CBO ₅ ²⁾	mgO ₂ /L	52	SR EN ISO 5815-1:2020
5	CCOCr ²⁾	mgO ₂ /L	180.4	SR ISO 6060:1996
6	Indice de permanganat*	mgO ₂ /L	0.39	Procedura operationala de lucru POL-02N
7	Amoniu	mg/L	0.35	SR ISO 7150-1:2001
8	Nitriti	mg/L	0.03	SR EN 26777:2002; SR EN 26777:2002/C91:2006
9	Azotati	mg/L	0.96	SR ISO 7890-3:2000
10	Azot total	mg/L	<1	SR EN ISO 20236:2021
11	Fosfati	mg/L	0.39	SR EN ISO 6878:2005, pct. 4
12	Fosfor total	mg/L	0.52	SR EN ISO 6878:2005, pct. 8
13	Conductivitate electrica la 25°C	µS/cm	2680	SR EN 27888:1997
14	Reziduu filtrabil uscat la 105°C (TDS)	mg/L	1790	STAS 9187-84
15	Cloruri	mg/L	379	SR ISO 9297:2001
16	Sulfati	mg/L	660	EPA 9038:1986
17	Calciu	mg/L	262	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
18	Magneziu	mg/L	142	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
19	Sodiu	mg/L	129	SR EN ISO 11885:2009

***incercare neacreditata RENAR**

¹⁾Acest indicator este insotit de temperatura la care s-a efectuat masurarea

²⁾Incercare executata in DCP-BIOL (Departament Control Poluare - Laborator Bioteste-Analize Biologice) – Drumul Podu Dambovitei nr. 57-73, sector 6, Bucuresti

Observatie:

- rezultatul notat cu "<" reprezinta valoarea situata sub limita de determinare a metodei.

DIRECTOR GENERAL,

Dr. Chim. Luciana Florentina PASCU

Sef Laborator,

Dr. Chim. Florentina Laura CHIRIAC

Cod PSL-7.8-F1/Ed2-R1

Nr. Crt	Incercare executată	UM	Simbol probă/ valori determinate	Metoda de încercare
			8056-AINS	
20	Fluoruri	mg/L	0.32	SR ISO 10359-1:2001
21	Crom total	µg/L	<2.0	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
22	Cupru	µg/L	8.3	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
23	Zinc	µg/L	5.5	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
24	Arsen	µg/L	<2.0	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
25	Bariu	µg/L	51.4	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
26	Cobalt	µg/L	<0.6	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
27	Plumb	µg/L	<2.0	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
28	Cadmiu	µg/L	<0.4	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
29	Fier total	µg/L	25.7	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
30	Seleniu	µg/L	<3.5	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
31	Mercur	µg/L	<0.01	SR EN ISO 17852:2008
32	Mangan	µg/L	37.2	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
33	Nichel	µg/L	2.7	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
34	Indice de fenol	mg/L	<0.002	SR ISO 6439:2001; SR ISO 6439:2001/C91:2006
35	Continut de produse petroliere	mg/L	<0.1	SR 7877-2:1995
36	Substante extractibile cu solventi	mg/L	<20	SR 7587:1996 cap 4; EPA 1664:2010, Rev. B, pct. 7.10
37	Policlorbifenili (PCB) suma congenerilor 28,52,101,118,138,153,180	µg/L	<0.005	SR EN ISO 6468:2000
38	Cianuri totale *	mg/L	<0.03	Procedura operationala de lucru POL-03N
39	Agenti de suprafata anionici - MBAS masurarea indicelui de albastru de metilen ²⁾	mg/L	<0.1	SR ISO 10260:1996

*incercare neacreditata RENAR

²⁾Incercare executata in DCP-BIOL (Departament Control Poluare - Laborator Bioteste-Analize Biologice) – Drumul Podu Dambovitei nr. 57-73, sector 6, Bucuresti

Observatie:

- rezultatul notat cu “<” reprezinta valoarea situata sub limita de determinare a metodei.

DIRECTOR GENERAL,
Dr. Chim. Luana Florentina PASCU

Sef Laborator,
Dr. Chim. Florentina Laura CHIRIAC

Cod PSL-7.8-F1/Ed2-R1

Nr. Crt	Incercare executată	UM	Simbol probă/ valori determinate	Metoda de încercare
			8056-AINS	
40	Trihalometani	µg/L	<0.1	ISO 20595:2018 (E)
	Cloroform	µg/L	<0.1	
41	BTEX	µg/L	<0.1	ISO 20595:2018 (E)
	Benzen	µg/L	<0.1	
	Toluen	µg/L	<0.1	
	Etilbenzen	µg/L	<0.1	
	(o,m,p)-Xileni	µg/L	<0.1	
42	Hidrocarburi halogenate foarte volatile	µg/L	<0.1	ISO 20595:2018 (E)
	Diclorometan	µg/L	<0.1	
	Tetraclorura de carbon (Tetraclorometan)	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,1-dicloroetan	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,2-dicloroetan	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,1,1-tricloroetan	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,1,2-tricloroetan	µg/L	<0.1	
	Tricloroetena	µg/L	<0.1	
	Tetracloroetena	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,2-dicloropropan	µg/L	<0.1	
43	Clorura de vinil*	µg/L	<0.1	Procedura operationala de lucru POL-12N
44	Clorobenzen	µg/L	<0.1	ISO 20595:2018 (E)
	1,2-diclorobenzen	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,3-diclorobenzen	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,4-diclorobenzen	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,2,3-triclorobenzen	µg/L	<0.1	

*incercare neacreditata RENAR

²⁾Incercare executata in DCP-BIOL (Departament Control Poluare - Laborator Bioteste-Analize Biologice) – Drumul Podu Dambovitei nr. 57-73, sector 6, Bucuresti

Observatie:

- rezultatul notat cu “<” reprezinta valoarea situata sub limita de determinare a metodei.

DIRECTOR GENERAL,

Dr. Chim. Luciana Florentina PASCU

Sef Laborator,

Dr. Chim. Florentina Laura CHIRIAC

Cod PSL-7.8-F1/Ed2-R1

Nr. Crt	Incercare executată	UM	Simbol probă/ valori determinate	Metoda de încercare
			8056-AINS	
45	Pesticide organoclorurate			SR EN ISO 6468:2000
	alfa-HCH	µg/L	<0.005	
	beta-HCH	µg/L	<0.005	
	gama-HCH	µg/L	<0.005	
	delta-HCH	µg/L	<0.005	
	4,4'-DDD	µg/L	<0.005	
	4,4'-DDT	µg/L	<0.005	
	4,4'-DDE	µg/L	<0.005	
	Heptaclor	µg/L	<0.005	
	Heptaclorepoxid	µg/L	<0.005	
	Aldrin	µg/L	<0.005	
	Dieldrin	µg/L	<0.005	
	Endrin	µg/L	<0.005	
	Alaclor	µg/L	<0.005	
alfa-endosulfan	µg/L	<0.005		
46	Pesticide triazinice*			Procedura operationala de lucru POL-07N
	Simazin*	µg/L	<0.025	
	Atrazin*	µg/L	<0.025	
	Propazin*	µg/L	<0.025	
47	Pesticide fosforice			SR EN 12918:2002
	Malation	µg/L	<0.003	
	Paration	µg/L	<0.003	
	Diclorvos	µg/L	<0.003	
	Diazinon	µg/L	<0.003	
	Clorfeninfos	µg/L	<0.003	
	Clorpirifos	µg/L	<0.003	
	Metamidofos	µg/L	<0.003	
	Mevinfos	µg/L	<0.003	

*incercare neacreditata RENAR

Observatie:

- rezultatul notat cu "<" reprezinta valoarea situata sub limita de determinare a metodei.

DIRECTOR GENERAL,
Dr. Chim. Luana Florentina PASCU

Sef laborator,
Dr. Chim. Florentina Laura CHIRIAC

Cod PSL-7.8-F1/Ed2-R1

Nr. Crt	Incercare executată	UM	Simbol probă/ valori determinate	Metoda de încercare
			8056-AINS	
48	Hidrocarburi aromatice policiclice (HAP)	µg/L	<0.002	SR EN ISO 17993:2004
	Antracen	µg/L	<0.002	
	Benz(a)antracen	µg/L	<0.002	
	Benz(b)fluoranten	µg/L	<0.002	
	Benz(k)fluoranten	µg/L	<0.002	
	Benz(ghi)perilen	µg/L	<0.002	
	Benz(a)piren	µg/L	<0.002	
	Crisen	µg/L	<0.002	
	Fluoranten	µg/L	<0.002	
	Indeno(1,2,3-cd)piren	µg/L	<0.002	
	Naftalina	µg/L	<0.002	
	Fenantren	µg/L	<0.002	
	Piren	µg/L	<0.002	

Observatie:

- rezultatul notat cu "<" reprezinta valoarea situata sub limita de determinare a metodei.

DIRECTOR GENERAL,
Dr. Chim. Luana Florentina PASCU

Sef laborator,
Dr. Chim. Florentina Laura CHIRIAC

RAPORT DE ÎNCERCARE Nr. 3465/2-AINS din 11.12.2024

Denumire și adresă client: AQUAPROIECT S.A. BUCURESTI,

Splaiul Independentei nr. 294, Sector 6, Bucuresti

Comanda nr.: 17607/11.11.2024

Data primirii probelor: 18.11.2024

Perioada executării încercărilor: 18.11.-05.12.2024

Date de identificare a probelor: apa uzata

8057-AINS - apa uzata – apa pluviala – Bazin TEP 2

Încercări executate: Temperatura, pH, Oxigen dizolvat, CBO₅, CCOCr, Indice de permanganat, Amoniu, Nitriti, Azotati, Azot total, Fosfati, Fosfor total, Conductivitate electrica la 25°C, Reziduu filtrabil uscat la 105°C (TDS), Cloruri, Sulfati, Calciu, Magneziu, Sodiu, Fluoruri, Crom total, Cupru, Zinc, Arsen, Bariu, Cobalt, Plumb, Cadmiu, Fier total, Seleniu, Mercur, Mangan, Nichel, Indice de fenol, Continut de produse petroliere, Substante extractibile cu solventi, Hidrocarburi aromatice policiclice (HAP): [Antracen, Benz(a)antracen, Benz(b)fluoranten, Benz(k)fluoranten, Benz(ghi)perilen, Benz(a)piren, Crisen, Fluoranten, Indeno(1,2,3-cd)piren, Naftalina, Fenantren, Piren], Pesticide organoclorurate: [alfa-HCH, beta-HCH, gama-HCH, delta-HCH, 4,4'-DDD, 4,4'-DDT, 4,4'-DDE, Heptaclor, Heptaclorepoxid, Aldrin, Dieldrin, Endrin, Alaclor, alfa-endosulfan], Pesticide triazinice: [Simazin, Atrazin, Propazin], Pesticide fosforice: [Malation, Paration, Diclorvos, Diazinon, Clorfenvinfos, Clorpirifos, Metamidofos, Mevinfos], Hidrocarburi halogenate foarte volatile: [Diclorometan, Tetraclorura de carbon, 1,1-dicloroetan, 1,2-dicloroetan, 1,1,1-tricloroetan, 1,1,2-tricloroetan, Tricloroetena, Tetracloroetena, 1,2-dicloropropan, Clorura de vinil], Clorobenzen, 1,2-diclorobenzen, 1,3-diclorobenzen, 1,4-diclorobenzen, 1,2,3-triclorobenzen, 1,2,4-triclorobenzen, Trihalometani (Cloroform), BTEX: [Benzen, Toluen, Etilbenzen, (o,m,p-Xileni)], Policlorbifenili (PCB) suma congenerilor 28,52,101,118,138,153,180, Cianuri totale, Agenti de suprafata anionici - MBAS masurarea indicelui de albastru de metilen.

Modul de prelevare și conservare a probei: Proba a fost prelevata de INCD-ECOIND conform Raportului de prelevare-conservare nr. Rpc. 388-BIOL/18.11.2024, respectandu-se indicatiile normativelor privind prelevarea, conservarea si transportul probelor de apa.

Rezultatele prezentate in Raportul de Incercare se refera numai la proba supusa incercarii.

Se interzice reproducerea Raportului de Incercare in alte scopuri decat cel pentru care a fost eliberat sau reproducerea partiala a Raportului de Incercare fara acordul scris al INCD-ECOIND.

Executant: Departament Control Poluare, Laborator Control Poluare Ape, Sol, Deseuri (AINS), Laborator Bioteste - Analize Biologice (BIOL)

DIRECTOR GENERAL,

Dr. Chim. Luciana Florentina PASCU

Sef Laborator,

Dr. Chim. Florentina Laura CHIRIAC

Raport de Incercare întocmit în 2 exemplare din care exemplarul 1 la client.

Acest raport va fi însoțit de Raportul de Incercare nr. 1035/1-BIOL/2024, emis de Laboratorul Bioteste-Analize biologice din Drumul Podu Dambovitei nr. 57-73, sector 6, Bucuresti avand Certificatul de acreditare LI941 - actualizat in data de 21.12.2023

Nr. Crt	Incercare executată	UM	Simbol probă/ valori determinate	Metoda de încercare
			8057-AINS	
1	Temperatura ²⁾ ,*	°C	15.9	Procedura operationala de lucru POL-46N
2	pH ^{1), 2)}	unitati de pH	7.7 20.9°C	SR EN ISO 10523:2012
3	Oxigen dizolvat ^{1), 2)} ,*	mgO ₂ /L	8.84 19.0°C	SR EN ISO 5814:2013
4	CBO ₅ ²⁾	mgO ₂ /L	8.4	SR EN ISO 5815-1:2020
5	CCOCr ²⁾	mgO ₂ /L	<30	SR ISO 6060:1996
6	Indice de permanganat*	mgO ₂ /L	0.43	Procedura operationala de lucru POL-02N
7	Amoniu	mg/L	<0.02	SR ISO 7150-1:2001
8	Nitriti	mg/L	0.01	SR EN 26777:2002; SR EN 26777:2002/C91:2006
9	Azotati	mg/L	8.85	SR ISO 7890-3:2000
10	Azot total	mg/L	<1	SR EN ISO 20236:2021
11	Fosfati	mg/L	0.42	SR EN ISO 6878:2005, pct. 4
12	Fosfor total	mg/L	0.72	SR EN ISO 6878:2005, pct. 8
13	Conductivitate electrica la 25°C	µS/cm	409	SR EN 27888:1997
14	Reziduu filtrabil uscat la 105°C (TDS)	mg/L	270	STAS 9187-84
15	Cloruri	mg/L	20.8	SR ISO 9297:2001
16	Sulfati	mg/L	36.8	EPA 9038:1986
17	Calciu	mg/L	31.8	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
18	Magneziu	mg/L	3.84	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
19	Sodiu	mg/L	51.2	SR EN ISO 11885:2009

***incercare neacreditata RENAR**

¹⁾Acest indicator este insotit de temperatura la care s-a efectuat masurarea

²⁾Incercare executata in DCP-BIOL (Departament Control Poluare - Laborator Bioteste-Analize Biologice) – Drumul Podu Dambovitei nr. 57-73, sector 6, Bucuresti

Observatie:

- rezultatul notat cu “<” reprezinta valoarea situata sub limita de determinare a metodei.

DIRECTOR GENERAL,

Dr. Chim. Luana Florentina PASCU

Sef Laborator,

Dr. Chim. Florentina Laura CHIRIAC

Cod PSL-7.8-F1/Ed2-R1

Nr. Crt	Incercare executată	UM	Simbol probă/ valori determinate	Metoda de încercare
			8057-AINS	
20	Fluoruri	mg/L	0.13	SR ISO 10359-1:2001
21	Crom total	µg/L	<2.0	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
22	Cupru	µg/L	10.5	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
23	Zinc	µg/L	166	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
24	Arsen	µg/L	<2.0	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
25	Bariu	µg/L	28.6	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
26	Cobalt	µg/L	1.7	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
27	Plumb	µg/L	<2.0	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
28	Cadmiu	µg/L	<0.4	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
29	Fier total	µg/L	1273	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
30	Seleniu	µg/L	<3.5	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
31	Mercur	µg/L	<0.01	SR EN ISO 17852:2008
32	Mangan	µg/L	13.0	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
33	Nichel	µg/L	2.2	SR EN ISO 11885:2009
34	Indice de fenol	mg/L	<0.002	SR ISO 6439:2001; SR ISO 6439:2001/C91:2006
35	Continut de produse petroliere	mg/L	<0.01	SR 7877-2:1995
36	Substante extractibile cu solvenți	mg/L	<20	SR 7587:1996 cap 4; EPA 1664:2010, Rev. B, pct. 7.10
37	Policlorbifenili (PCB) suma congenerilor 28,52,101,118,138,153,180	µg/L	<0.005	SR EN ISO 6468:2000
38	Cianuri totale *	mg/L	<0.03	Procedura operationala de lucru POL-03N
39	Agenti de suprafata anionici - MBAS masurarea indicelui de albastru de metilen ²⁾	mg/L	<0.1	SR ISO 10260:1996

*incercare neacreditata RENAR

²⁾Incercare executata in DCP-BIOL (Departament Control Poluare - Laborator Bioteste-Analize Biologice) – Drumul Podu Dambovitei nr. 57-73, sector 6, Bucuresti

Observatie:

- rezultatul notat cu "<" reprezinta valoarea situata sub limita de determinare a metodei.

DIRECTOR GENERAL,
Dr. Chim. Iuliana Florentina PASCU

Sef Laborator,
Dr. Chim. Florentina Laura CHIRIAC

Cod PSL-7.8-F1/Ed2-R1

Nr. Crt	Incercare executată	UM	Simbol probă/ valori determinate	Metoda de încercare
			8057-AINS	
40	Trihalometani	µg/L	<0.1	ISO 20595:2018 (E)
	Cloroform	µg/L	<0.1	
41	BTEX	µg/L	<0.1	ISO 20595:2018 (E)
	Benzen	µg/L	<0.1	
	Toluen	µg/L	<0.1	
	Etilbenzen	µg/L	<0.1	
	(o,m,p)-Xileni	µg/L	<0.1	
42	Hidrocarburi halogenate foarte volatile	µg/L	<0.1	ISO 20595:2018 (E)
	Diclorometan	µg/L	<0.1	
	Tetraclorura de carbon (Tetraclorometan)	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,1-dicloroetan	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,2-dicloroetan	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,1,1-tricloroetan	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,1,2-tricloroetan	µg/L	<0.1	
	Tricloroetena	µg/L	<0.1	
	Tetracloroetena	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,2-dicloropropan	µg/L	<0.1	
43	Clorura de vinil*	µg/L	<0.1	Procedura operationala de lucru POL-12N
44	Clorobenzen	µg/L	<0.1	ISO 20595:2018 (E)
	1,2-diclorobenzen	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,3-diclorobenzen	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,4-diclorobenzen	µg/L	<0.1	
	1,2,3-triclorobenzen	µg/L	<0.1	

*incercare neacreditata RENAR

²⁾Incercare executata in DCP-BIOL (Departament Control Poluare - Laborator Bioteste-Analize Biologice) – Drumul Podu Dambovitei nr. 57-73, sector 6, Bucuresti

Observatie:

- rezultatul notat cu “<” reprezinta valoarea situata sub limita de determinare a metodei.

DIRECTOR GENERAL

Dr. Chim. Luciana Florentina PASCU

Sef Laborator,

Dr. Chim. Florentina Laura CHIRIAC

Cod PSL-7.8-F1/Ed2-R1

Nr. Crt	Incercare executată	UM	Simbol probă/ valori determinate	Metoda de încercare
			8057-AINS	
45	Pesticide organoclorurate			SR EN ISO 6468:2000
	alfa-HCH	µg/L	<0.005	
	beta-HCH	µg/L	<0.005	
	gama-HCH	µg/L	<0.005	
	delta-HCH	µg/L	<0.005	
	4,4'-DDD	µg/L	<0.005	
	4,4'-DDT	µg/L	<0.005	
	4,4'-DDE	µg/L	<0.005	
	Heptaclor	µg/L	<0.005	
	Heptaclorepoxid	µg/L	<0.005	
	Aldrin	µg/L	<0.005	
	Dieldrin	µg/L	<0.005	
	Endrin	µg/L	<0.005	
	Alaclor	µg/L	<0.005	
alfa-endosulfan	µg/L	<0.005		
46	Pesticide triazinice*			Procedura operationala de lucru POL-07N
	Simazin*	µg/L	<0.025	
	Atrazin*	µg/L	<0.025	
	Propazin*	µg/L	<0.025	
47	Pesticide fosforice			SR EN 12918:2002
	Malation	µg/L	<0.003	
	Paration	µg/L	<0.003	
	Diclorvos	µg/L	<0.003	
	Diazinon	µg/L	<0.003	
	Clorfenvinfos	µg/L	<0.003	
	Clorpirifos	µg/L	<0.003	
	Metamidofos	µg/L	<0.003	
Mevinfos	µg/L	<0.003		

*incercare neacreditata RENAR

Observatie:

- rezultatul notat cu "<" reprezinta valoarea situata sub limita de determinare a metodei.

DIRECTOR GENERAL,
Dr. Chim. Lucreia Florentina PASCU

Sef laborator,
Dr. Chim. Florentina Laura CHIRIAC

Nr. Crt	Incercare executată	UM	Simbol probă/ valori determinate	Metoda de încercare
			8057-AINS	
48	Hidrocarburi aromatice policiclice (HAP)	µg/L	<0.002	SR EN ISO 17993:2004
	Antracen	µg/L	<0.002	
	Benz(a)antracen	µg/L	<0.002	
	Benz(b)fluoranten	µg/L	<0.002	
	Benz(k)fluoranten	µg/L	<0.002	
	Benz(ghi)perilen	µg/L	<0.002	
	Benz(a)piren	µg/L	<0.002	
	Crisen	µg/L	<0.002	
	Fluoranten	µg/L	<0.002	
	Indeno(1,2,3-cd)piren	µg/L	<0.002	
	Naftalina	µg/L	<0.002	
	Fenantren	µg/L	<0.002	
	Piren	µg/L	<0.002	

Observatie:

- rezultatul notat cu "<" reprezinta valoarea situata sub limita de determinare a metodei.

DIRECTOR GENERAL,

Dr. Chim. Luana Florentina PASCU

Sef laborator,

Dr. Chim. Florentina Laura CHIRIAC

RAPORT DE INCERCARE
Nr. 1035/1-BIOL din 21.11.2024

Denumire si adresa client: SC AQUAPROIECT SA
Str. Splaiul Independentei nr. 294, Sector 6, Bucuresti

Comanda Dvs. nr. 3170 din 11.11.2024 (e-mail), inregistrata la INCD ECOIND cu nr. 17607/11.11.2024

Data primirii probelor: 18.11.2024 **Perioada executarii incercarilor: 18.11.2024 – 21.11.2024**
Date de identificare a probelor: 3188-BIOL - apa de suprafata – apa din iazurile din Parcul Natural Vacaresti

Incercari executate: bacterii coliforme totale, bacterii coliforme fecale, enterococi (streptococi fecali).
Modul de prelevare si conservare a probelor: Proba a fost prelevata de specialistii INCD-ECOIND Bucuresti, in recipient steril, in data de 18.11.2024, conform *Raport de prelevare-conservare nr. 388-BIOL/18.11.2024* si receptionata la sediul institutului in aceeasi zi, in vederea efectuarii incercarilor bacteriologice, respectandu-se indicatiile normativelor privind prelevarea, conservarea si transportul probelor de apa.

Nr crt	Incercare executata	U.M.	Simbol proba / Valori determinate	Metoda de incercare
			3188-BIOL	
1	Bacterii coliforme totale	Numar probabil/100mL	84 x 10 ²	SR EN ISO 9308-2:2014
2	Bacterii coliforme fecale	Numar probabil/100mL	3	
3	Enterococi (streptococi fecali)	Numar/100mL	0	SR EN ISO 7899-2:2002

Rezultatele prezentate in Raportul de Incercare se refera numai la probele supuse incercarii. Se interzice reproducerea Raportului de Incercare in alte scopuri decat cel pentru care a fost eliberat sau reproducerea partiala a Raportului de Incercare fara acordul scris al INCD-ECOIND.

Observatii:

- *Ordinul nr. 161 din 16.02.2006 nu prezinta valori normate pentru indicatorii microbiologici.*

Executant: Departamentul Control Poluare - Laboratorul Bioteste – Analize Biologice

DIRECTOR GENERAL,
Dr. chim. Luoana Florentina Pascu

SEF LABORATOR,
Dr. biol. Alina-Roxana Banciu

Raport de Incercare intocmit in 2 exemplare din care exemplarul 1 la client.
Acest Raport va fi insotit de Raportul de Incercare nr. 3465/1-AINS/2024, emis de Laboratorul Control Poluare Apa, Sol, Deseuri din Drumul Podu Dambovitei nr. 57-73, Sector 6, Bucuresti avand Certificatul de acreditare LI941 - actualizat in data de 21.12.2023.

RAPORT DE INCERCARE
Nr. 1035/2-BIOL din 21.11.2024

Denumire si adresa client: SC AQUAPROIECT SA
Str. Splaiul Independentei nr. 294, Sector 6, Bucuresti

Comanda Dvs. nr. 3170 din 11.11.2024 (e-mail), inregistrata la INCD ECOIND cu nr. 17607/11.11.2024

Data primirii probelor: 18.11.2024 **Perioada executarii incercarilor:** 18.11.2024 – 21.11.2024

Date de identificare a probelor: 3189-BIOL - apa uzata – Bazin TEP 2 (apa pluviala)

Incercari executate: bacterii coliforme totale, bacterii coliforme fecale, enterococi (streptococi fecali).

Modul de prelevare si conservare a probelor: Proba a fost prelevata de specialistii INCD-ECOIND Bucuresti, in recipient steril, in data de 18.11.2024, conform *Raport de prelevare-conservare nr. 388-BIOL/18.11.2024* si receptionata la sediul institutului in aceeasi zi, in vederea efectuării incercarilor bacteriologice, respectandu-se indicatiile normativelor privind prelevarea, conservarea si transportul probelor de apa.

Nr ert	Incercare executata	U.M.	Simbol proba / Valori determinate	Metoda de incercare
			3189-BIOL	
1	Bacterii coliforme totale	Numar probabil/100mL	1 x 10 ²	SR EN ISO 9308-2:2014
2	Bacterii coliforme fecale	Numar probabil/100mL	2	
3	Enterococi (streptococi fecali)	Numar/100mL	0	SR EN ISO 7899-2:2002

Rezultatele prezentate in Raportul de Incercare se refera numai la probele supuse incercarii. Se interzice reproducerea Raportului de Incercare in alte scopuri decat cel pentru care a fost eliberat sau reproducerea partiala a Raportului de Incercare fara acordul scris al INCD-ECOIND.

Observatii: -

Executant: Departamentul Control Poluare - Laboratorul Bioteste – Analize Biologice

DIRECTOR GENERAL,
Dr. chim. Luana Florentina Pascu

SEF LABORATOR,
Dr. biol. Alina-Roxana Banciu

Raport de Incercare intocmit in 2 exemplare din care exemplarul 1 la client.

Acest Raport va fi insotit de Raportul de Incercare nr. 3465/2-AINS/2024, emis de Laboratorul Control Poluare Apa, Sol, Deseuri din Drumul Podu Dambovitei nr. 57-73, Sector 6, Bucuresti avand Certificatul de acreditare LI941 - actualizat in data de 21.12.2023.

Annex 2 – Quality Standards and Analytical Equipment

The sampling/preservation activity for ensuring the representativeness of the results of analytical investigations was carried out according to the provisions of the Water Quality standards.

Sampling for physico-chemical and microbiological analyses:

SR ISO 5667-1:2023 Water quality. Sampling. Part 1: General guide for the establishment of sampling programs and techniques.

SR EN ISO 5667–3: 2018 Water quality. Sampling. Part 3: Preservation and handling of water samples.

SR ISO 5667-4:2020 Water quality. Sampling. Part 4: Guide for the sampling of water from natural and artificial lakes.

SR ISO 5667-5:2017 Water quality. Sampling. Part 5: Guide for the sampling of drinking water from treatment plants and distribution networks

SR EN ISO 5667-6:2017 Water quality. Sampling. Part 6: Guide for sampling in rivers and other watercourses.

SR EN ISO 5667-6:2017/A11:2020 Water quality. Sampling. Part 6: Guide for sampling in rivers and other watercourses.

SR ISO 5667-10:2021 Calitatea apei. Prelevare. Partea 10: Water quality. Sampling. Part 10: Guide for the sampling of wastewater.

ISO 5667-11:2009 Calitatea apei. Prelevare. Partea 11: Water quality. Sampling. Part 11: Guide for the sampling of groundwater.

SR EN ISO 19458:2007 Water quality. Sampling for microbiological analysis

The physico-chemical and microbiological analyses were performed according to the specific standards mentioned in the characterization tables presented in Annex 1. The

analytical equipment/instruments potentially used¹ for performing the determinations are as follows:

- UV-VIS Spectrometer Perkin Elmer, Lambda 25 (anions);
- ICP-OES Spectrometer Perkin Elmer Optima (metals);
- AAS Spectrometer Solar M6 Dual Thermo Electron (sodium);
- Mercury Analyzer Cetak/M800 Quic Trace (mercury);
- Gas Chromatograph with Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer GC7890B, QQQ 7010B Agilent (THM);
- Gas Chromatograph Agilent 7890A with μ -ECD and FPD (chlorinated, phosphoric, triazine pesticides);
- Liquid Chromatograph Agilent 1100 with FLD, MWD (HAP);
- TOC Analyzer VARIO, Elementar;
- Multiparameter WTW 340i (pH, conductivity);
- Fluorometer WTW INOLAB (fluoride);
- Oven BMT Venticel and Analytical Balance Precisa XT 220A;
- COV Analyzer Analysentechnik GMBH;
- AOX Analyzer Thermo Electron, type Dextar;
- Analytical Balance Kern ABT220-5DM.

¹ The listed analytical equipment/instruments can be found on the laboratory's website.

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